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IN-VITRO GASTRIC EXTRACTION TO EVALUATE METAL BIOACCESSIBILITY AND HUMAN EXPOSURE FROM URBAN SOILS AFFECTED BY MULTIPLE METAL PATHWAYS (HUELVA, SW SPAIN)

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>The main purpose of this study was to assess the human health risk of heavy metals in the urban-periurban soils from Huelva Township. The soils present high concentrations of potentially toxic elements well beyond the regional screening soil concentration. A site-specific health risk assessment of exposure (oral ingestion, oral inhalation and dermal contact) was conducted according to the regulatory normative. To reduce the uncertainty derived from soil characteristics, bioaccessibility and predicted bioavailability data were included in the assessment. Thereby, in order to evaluate the oral bioaccessibility, a simulation of the gastric condition (pH and T) was applied dissolving the samples in a solution of HCl and 0,4M glycine. Soils located in industrial areas present higher bioaccessibility than those associated to urban or other uses. The adjusted-RBA total carcinogenic risk for As exceeded the regulatory level in all samples (except samples 7 and 184) indicating that children are more vulnerable, while no detrimental health effects are expected for Pb (except in sample 76, a "greenway" recreational area). The adjusted-BAC hazard index for non-carcinogenic</p>	

	<p>effects also overpassed the threshold values in practically all possible scenarios for and adult resident working in Huelva, as well as for a child living and playing in the urban/recreational areas. The main pollutant contributions were related to As and Pb. For this reason, the reported soils exceeding the regulatory levels should be classified as polluted and, therefore, this study should be helpful to initiate necessary soil management interventions to avoid the human health risk.</p>
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	<p>Response to reviewers</p> <p>Reviewer #1: The manuscript deals with an interesting subject related to ecological and human health risks associated with exposure to potentially toxic elements (PTE) in urban and periurban soils of an industrial city. The authors tried to evaluate the oral bioaccessibility of PTE using experimental results from a glycine-buffered test in combination with generic reference levels calculated from basic descriptive statistics. The paper also compares the bioaccessibility with the chemical fractionation of PTE based on data of a previous study. The impact of PTE on the soil quality of residential communities is an important environmental health research concern. Thus, I find the topic relevant for submission in the journal. However, in my view the objectives are unclear and confusing, and the study design seems to be inappropriate to obtaining valid and scientifically sound results. I feel the manuscript suffers from some important flaws that do not allow the authors to address all the objectives set in the introduction.</p> <p>Firstly, one of the main objectives of the study was to determine the generic reference levels (GRL), which are defined in the Spanish regulation on contaminated soils (Royal Decree 9/2005). The authors used a statistical method for setting the GRL ($X + 2SD$, where X is the average element concentration and SD is the typical standard deviation of the concentrations in soils not contaminated with similar geological substrates). This approach is inadequate and obsolete. In 2015, the Autonomous Government of Andalusia issued the GRL for assessing contamination by PTE in soils of such region. These statutory levels meet the criteria established in the Annex VII of the Royal Decree 9/2005 and they are the basic parameters that the authors should have used for assessing soil contamination around the city of Huelva. Thus, if a comparison to the GRL established under the regulatory Andalusian framework is performed, the values calculated by the authors are considerably lower (by two or three orders of magnitude for most PTE), and do not exceeded the health-based reference values for industrial and urban land uses. To this reviewer, the regional screening levels should be used to identify potential polluted areas that require site-specific risk analysis. In these areas, the incorporation of site-specific bioaccessibility estimates could be useful to reduce the uncertainty in quantitative risk assessment.</p> <p>The authors totally agree with the reviewer. The recommendation has been carefully followed in order to improve the quality of the manuscript. In this line, a new complete approach has been developed to determine the human risk exposure in the study area. Also, in order to reduce the uncertainty in this calculation, the bioaccessibility and adjusted bioavailability have been used.</p> <p>But my major concern is about the used methodology. The soil samples were taken during the fall 2007. Thirteen years have passed since then! The authors should have been aware that the recommended maximum holding time for samples that have been properly preserved is six months from the sample collection until extraction.</p> <p>The authors would like to note that all treatment and analytical protocol were applied between 2007 and 2011, in the same project that other analyses (SEP-BCR) used in the manuscript, however due to several circumstances the results have been processed nowadays.</p> <p>To improve the understanding of the methodology the new version of the manuscript has been rewritten:</p> <p>Lines 135-136. The sentence has been corrected as following: "A number of selected samples were evaluated in 2011 by the in vitro extraction technique and analysed for As, Cd, Co, Cr, Ni, Cu, Pb and Zn by ICP-MS determination".</p> <p>Moreover, I was surprised to see that the samples were passed through a 63 µm sieve for the bioaccessibility assay. The <250 µm is the most commonly used grain-size fraction for in-vitro digestion tests following USEPA guidelines. This fact should be considered. Otherwise, the results from this study cannot be directly comparable with the standard guideline values.</p>

This paragraph has been corrected, since the sample was not sieved two times in the protocol, but it was milled above 63µm with agate mortar for analyses purpose. Also, the fraction <2mm has been used in other studies related to environmental or human risk assessment. In fact, the regional baseline (Galán et al., 2008) and reference values (Junta de Andalucía, 2015) were determined over < 2mm samples, justifying the use of this fraction for comparative purpose.

Lines 139-131. The sentence has been corrected as follows: "Each sample was dried in an oven at 40 °C to avoid loss of volatiles, it was fragmented using a wooden roller and then sieved through a 2 mm mesh, homogenized, milled at 63 µm and refrigerated (4 °C) in a polypropylene container until analysis".

This reviewer agrees on the view that bioaccessibility of PTE depends on mineral composition and soil properties (pH, redox potential, organic matter, clay content, cation exchange capacity, etc.). In this regard, it would be very useful to conduct a soil characterization. The lack of soil information makes difficult to properly interpret variations of bioaccessibility among different PTE and soils.

The authors agree the reviewer that the soil characterization is necessary in determined studies, mainly ecological. However, it is certain that according to recent studies, to reduce the uncertainty in quantitative risk assessment derived from the variability of the speciation of contaminant induced by soil properties (Darko et al., 2017) bioaccessibility and relative bioavailability are introduced in risk calculations (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

Also, according to the current legal framework (Royal Degree, 2005; Junta de Andalucía, 2015), the intrinsic properties of soils are not taken into account in GRL.

In order to clarify this aspect, the new version of the manuscript has been rewritten: Line 355-360: "The equations used to determine the chronic daily doses assume 100% bioavailability of the ingested soil-borne contaminant, but soil properties such as pH, texture, and organic matter, define the metal speciation and thus their bioavailability (Darko et al., 2017). Hence, to reduce the uncertainty in quantitative risk assessment, the site-specific bioaccessibility estimated from the gastric extraction has incorporated in our risk analysis, due to it could consider as the fraction of the PTE that an individual is exposed to upon soil ingestion (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019)".

In this study, the metal bioaccessibility in soil was determined by a single-step extraction test by using 0.4 M glycine as a buffer. This simplified in-vitro bioaccessibility method is not validated and simulates only a few aspects of the human gastrointestinal tract. Several studies have shown that with using a glycine-buffered method, interactions between iron and glycine may influence the concentration of arsenic in solution, which may not be consistent with human gastrointestinal conditions. This reviewer believes that the choice of a physiologically-based unified method (UBM), such as that proposed by the Bioaccessibility Research Group of Europe (BARGE), is more appropriate to achieve representative bioaccessibility values for estimating risks to human health. The validated UBM method is the most robust and applicable to different soil types and it becomes a widely accepted method in European countries to estimate bioaccessibility. There are soil reference materials (QC samples) available on the market for in-vitro essays. NIST 2710 and 2711 are the most commonly used in bioaccessibility extractions. Why these standard reference materials have not used to check the accuracy of the gastric extraction?

The reviewer comment has been taking into account, and the discussion can be found in the paragraph Bioaccessibility of potential toxic elements (Lines 309 - 317).

Also, the manuscript suffers from conceptual flaws. Inconsistency and imprecision are apparent when the terms bioaccessibility and bioavailability are used. Bioaccessibility and bioavailability have been used interchangeably in the introduction section causing confusion to readers.

The introduction has been re-written to clarify the confuse aspects. The use of bioaccessibility and bioavailability has been revised in the new version.

Bioaccessibility is not a tool to evaluate the potential toxicity of metals, as claimed by the authors in the abstract. The term bioavailability should also be removed from the manuscript, because the fraction of PTE absorbed and able to reach systemic

circulation in an organism has, in fact, not been studied.

The used of bioaccessibility and bioavailability has been revised in the new version. As can be previously denoted the result of the IVBA has been used to estimate the RBA.

This reviewer do not agree on the usage of the F1 fraction extracted by the BCR sequential extraction procedure as the bioavailable fraction.

Considerably more research will need to be undertaken to determine whether the soil contamination pose a risk to human health. The authors talk of risks, but the modeling does not seem complete to me and needs further elaboration in terms of relevant exposure pathways, exposure factors, toxicological data and health implications. The risk for humans connected with the pathway dermal contact, inhalation, and leaching to the groundwater of PTE should be considered in the evaluation.

A complete model including different exposure pathways has been developed, and then the on-site human health risk has been established for both adults and children receptors.

If not, the human health risk might be highly misleading and highly underestimated. The authors do not present any results concerning the quantitative carcinogenic risk of arsenic.

I certainly agree with the authors' statement that "an exhaustive review of the results obtained through in-vitro tests suggests the need to continue improving the risk assessment".

The previous answer can be consulted.

Therefore, I am concerned about the amount of unsupported generalizations and speculations contained within this manuscript. This is in part because the results, interpretations and conclusions are based on a questionable methodology. The authors extend their discussion beyond the findings supported by substantial evidence.

Lastly, the authors should do a better job of reviewing literature to establish the context of the work being reported looking at the recent advances in the field, as well in the context of the previously existing work. With regard to this last point, I suggest the authors survey the local and regional geochemical data on soils and sediments around Huelva, by CSIC, IGME and Junta de Andalucía, among others, as well the human health risks associated with trace elements in the area.

A careful review of the literature has been made in the new version of the manuscript.

Based on all the above considerations, I am afraid that I cannot recommend this manuscript for publication in Environmental Geochemical and Health.

Reviewer #2:

Dear authors and editor Dr Bech, here I have found a very interesting and innovative investigation about Huelva soils pollution, which I think it is unedited and necessary in such a complex area affected by multiple pollution. Despite the actual version has (for me) an overall score of 65 and needs a further review, I hope my comments will help for obtaining a refereed work in this subject of, at least, 90. For this reason, I suggest its acceptance after major revisions, that hereby I attached.

GENERAL COMMENTS

1-The English language must be reviewed. there are many little mistakes like "s" endings in adjectives instead of nouns, wrong use of prepositions or verbal tenses. I list some of them among the specific corrections, but there are only some examples, so the new version has to be carefully checked to avoid them.
A detailed review of the English language has been done.

2- The references have not been well checked. There are many references lost in the

bibliography section and vice versa. Remember to pay attention to reference included in tables.

A careful review of the literature and the reference list has been developed in the new version of the manuscript.

SPECIFIC COMMENTS

TITLE: GENERIC REFERENCE LEVELS, MULTIPLE METAL PATHWAYS

The title has been corrected and adjusted to the new version of the manuscript.

Line 32: assess the risk associated to health... this methodology is proved to be...

This line has been corrected.

Line 33: better results than

The sentence has been corrected.

INTRODUCTION

Line 55: Bosso and Enzweiler, 2008. Correct reference

Corrected.

Line 64: The implication caused by PTEs on human...

The sentence has been corrected.

Line 66: in the present work, specifically referred to bioaccessibility, is not recommendable to use here the term "bioavailable" for absorption once the elements are in the stomach, since this is the oral bioaccessibility. I recommend the work of Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019 in Chemosphere to give light on this terms, since there are other pathways of bioaccessibility not studied here such dermic adsorption or inhalation.

The authors agree with the reviewer. The recommendation has been followed in order to improve the quality of the manuscript. The introduction and the references to the bioaccessibility and/or bioavailability have been revised and clarified in the text.

Lines 78-82: Please review the writing to clear this sentence.

"In this sense, it is crucial distinguish among geogenic and anthropogenic trace elements input in soil for determining whether when a soil is polluted (Galán et al., 2014; Petrick et al., 2018)"

This assertion has been removed in the new version of the introduction.

Lines 85-89: The authors must review the current normative. In Spain there exists many NGRs but the Autonomic Governrs are the responsible of their regularization. In Andalusia search the RD 18/2015 were you will find the calculation of NGR and the metal and arsenic values obtained to use in this work.

The authors agree with the reviewer and the current normative has been used to estimate the specific site of study area that could require a remediation.

Then, please review the calculation of your values with this instructions, and use Andalusian values to compare your local Data, better than other studies of non official publications (review your text and table 2 and 3)

According to both revisor recommendations, the current legal framework (Junta de Andalucía, 2015) has been applied to determine the human risk exposure in the study area. Also, in order to reduce the uncertainty in this calculation, the bioaccessibility and adjusted bioavailability have been used.

All material related to this new approach can be seen in the new version of the manuscript.

Line 96-99: check writing.

The introduction has been re-written to clarify the confuse aspects.

Line 104: (3) Obtaining the bioaccessible values and comparing

This sentence has been removed in the R1 version.

AREA OF STUDY

Check references

The references have been checked.

Line 142: If you use only the fraction under 63 μm , you will probably overestimate the concentration values. Maybe you should justify the use of this fraction further, since this is the fraction that will more probably be coating ground vegetables that human will consume...

This paragraph has been corrected, since the sample was not sieved two times in the protocol, but it was milled above 63 μm with agate mortar for analyses purpose. Also, the fraction <2mm has been used in other studies related to environmental or human risk assessment. In fact, the regional baseline (Galán et al., 2008) and reference values (Junta de Andalucía, 2015) were determined over < 2mm samples, justifying the use of this fraction for comparative purpose.

Lines 139-131. The sentence has been corrected as follows: "Each sample was dried in an oven at 40 °C to avoid loss of volatiles, it was fragmented using a wooden roller and then sieved through a 2 mm mesh, homogenized, milled at 63 μm and refrigerated (4 °C) in a polypropylene container until analysis"

Lines 148-151: check writing.

Line 137-139. The sentence has been clarified.

Line 197: why do you refer to pseudototal If you are accounting the residual fraction? Please review this paragraph (Lines 202-209) because I think you are mixing SEPs with different number of steps and thus the confusion of terms.

The authors understand the interpretation of the reviewer. For this reason, the sentence has been completed for a better understanding (Lines 183-186). The reviewer should consider that in F1 of modified SEP-BCR the extractant (acetic acid 0.11 M solution) lixiviates the water/acid soluble and exchangeable fraction, including carbonate.

Line 214: here I recommend adding Andalusian values.

The GRL proposed by Autonomous Government of Andalusia have been used for assessing soil contamination in the study area.

Line 222: Please check the method of calculation of NGR because I think you have adopted the one of baselines, which is different.

The obsolete methodological approach has been replaced by a risk assessment model based in the current normative.

Line 232: F1+F2+F3 You´d better not use "mobile" for this sum, since it is incorrect. Mobile is more than bioavailable, so If F1 is potentially bioavailable, 1+2+3 would not be simply "mobile" instead anterior authors have given this name, it is not too real.

The term mobile fraction has been replaced by available fraction. Line 221. The paragraph 229-236 has been rewritten to improve the understanding, and the used terminology has been unified.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Line 258: in the Fig.2

Done. Line 244.

Line 285-288: check writing, not clear meaning. Figure 3 As is not clear: wy are there 2

trend lines? Moreover, the one of squares is deviated due to an anomalous value you should avoid.

This paragraph has been rewritten (Lines 269-274) and Figure 3 has been edited to clarify the correspondence of trend lines. However, the anomalous value of As has not been suppressed since sample (76) is located in an old mineral port. The authors think that this site needs to be highlighted for controlling because pseudototal concentration of As and Pb overpass the regulatory level established by Autonomous Government of Andalusia.

Line 293-294: check writing

This sentence has been removed in the R1 version.

Line 295-296: what does "limitations inherent in (to?) the BCR"? You allude to many inefficiencies on the extraction process, but do you think that yours had these problems? Are then yours not reliable results? Please clarify these aspects.

The authors would like to note that this affirmation only aims to support the used of bioaccessibility methodological approach in contrast to the above-mentioned traditional approach using F1 or total content in risk analyses. Anyway, the sentence has been substituted in the R1 version.

PARAGRAPH 3.2

Paragraph 305 on. check writing ...Determined. The highest risk for the human health...

The rest of the paragraph should be checked.

Checked.

Fig. 4: please explain better the meaning of the different sub-figures so the reader can understand the importance of seeing 3 different figures, by adding a short explanation in the footnote of the figure about the practical meaning of %Bac, F1/Bac... better than these acronyms. What do you want to show in these three figures? Are all necessary? Why?

The footnote as well as the terminology has been detailed and revised. In the new version of the manuscript the figure 4c has been eliminated due to its short information.

PARAGRAPH 3.3

Line 358-414: Check the part of the environmental implications for corrections after adding current normative of Andalusian Govern (RD 18/2005) and actualization of Spanish Law 22/2011 and PRA/1080/2017.

The paragraph related to environmental implications has been adapted according to the current normative of Andalusian Govern (RD 18/2005) and the risk assessment developed.

Paragraph 415 on: have you studied the risk associated to your ingestion data? Could you try to do it?

A complex model to determine human risk, taking into account three pathways including oral ingestion, inhalation ingestion and dermal adsorption, has been done. The methodological approach and the results obtained can be seen in the paragraphs 2.5, 3.4 and 3.5.

Line 424: "bioavailability" is bioaccessibility

Done.

FINAL REMARKS

You have forgotten to conclude you have made an inedited work on obtaining "NGR" for a locality. You should also include the risk of metals entering the human by gastric

ingestion.

Line 450: Wish only graphically represent what you have found, it does not reveal the data.

Corrected.

Line 464: if you could include data of the risk associated to in vitro extraction you would have to "suggest" that is a powerful tool, bt you could "confirm" it.

The R1 version of the manuscript include data of the risk calculated with RBA and BAC.

As a result of the significant disruption that is being caused by the COVID-19 pandemic we are very aware that many researchers will have difficulty in meeting the timelines associated with our peer review process during normal times. Please do let us know if you need additional time. Our systems will continue to remind you of the original timelines but we intend to be highly flexible at this time.

[Click here to view linked References](#)

1 **IN-VITRO GASTRIC EXTRACTION TO EVALUATE METAL BIOACCESSIBILITY AND HUMAN**
2 **EXPOSURE FROM URBAN SOILS AFFECTED BY MULTIPLE METAL PATHWAYS (HUELVA, SW**
3 **SPAIN)**

4
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16
17
18 **Abstract**

19 The main purpose of this study was to assess the human health risk of heavy metals in the urban-periurban soils
20 from Huelva Township. The soils present high concentrations of potentially toxic elements well beyond the regional
21 screening soil concentration. A site-specific health risk assessment of exposure (oral ingestion, oral inhalation and
22 dermal contact) was conducted according to the regulatory normative. To reduce the uncertainty derived from soil
23 characteristics, bioaccessibility and predicted bioavailability data were included in the assessment. Thereby, in order
24 to evaluate the oral bioaccessibility, a simulation of the gastric condition (pH and T) was applied dissolving the
25 samples in a solution of HCl and 0,4M glycine. Soils located in industrial areas present higher bioaccessibility than
26 those associated to urban or other uses. The adjusted-RBA total carcinogenic risk for As exceeded the regulatory
27 level in all samples (except samples 7 and 184) indicating that children are more vulnerable, while no detrimental
28 health effects are expected for Pb (except in sample 76, a "greenway" recreational area). The adjusted-BAC hazard
29 index for non-carcinogenic effects also overpassed the threshold values in practically all possible scenarios for and
30 adult resident working in Huelva, as well as for a child living and playing in the urban/recreational areas. The main
31 pollutant contributions were related to As and Pb. For this reason, the reported soils exceeding the regulatory levels
32 should be classified as polluted and, therefore, this study should be helpful to initiate necessary soil management
33 interventions to avoid the human health risk.

34
35 **Keyword:** Urban soil, *in vitro* extraction, metal bioaccessibility, human health risk, Carcinogenic metal.

36 **1. Introduction**

37

38 The generation of potentially dangerous substances currently represents a problem of global dimensions,
39 whose origin lies mainly in industrial production and distribution. As a result, the environment where
40 these activities take place has been affected by potentially toxic elements (PTEs) which could be harmful
41 to human health and ecosystems (Gupta et al., 1996). Currently, one of the most worrisome problems
42 about soil pollution is represented by heavy metals, as they can go unnoticed and then accumulate to
43 toxic levels (Rahaman et al., 2013). Thereby, Galán et al. (2019) assume that the mobile fractions of PTEs
44 in a soil and their bioavailability are the key factors to consider in any sort of risk assessment, devaluating
45 the “traditional” methods of estimation.

46 Historically, studies of soils contaminated by PTEs have been based on determined total or pseudototal
47 concentration to know their potential hazardous. Analogous, an extended method to evaluate the risk of
48 contaminated soils is to estimate the Generic Reference Levels (GRL), which established a values range
49 that can be used as indicators for the management of soils affected by pollutants. GRL establishes a
50 maximum level above which there may be a risk of adverse effects on health and the environment and
51 protective actions to reduce the risk should be required. In this line, according to the regulatory normative
52 in Spain (The Royal Decree 9/2005 of 14 January 2005) to declare a soil contaminated, the Autonomous
53 Government of Andalusia established in the Decree 18/2015 of 27 January 2015 (Junta de Andalucía,
54 2015) the GRL for assessing regional soil contamination. Some authors (Poggio et al., 2009; Okorie et al.,
55 2011; Sialelli et al., 2010; 2011) successfully supported the existence of a good correlation between the
56 pseudototal content and the bioaccessible fraction something to a methodological approach to determine
57 the potential hazardousness of PTEs (Romic and Romic, 2003). However, the concentration, by itself, of
58 an element cannot be taken as a reliable criterion for the evaluation of potential risks to health, due to
59 considering the potential large difference between oral bioavailability and total trace element content
60 routinely measured, human exposure to soil contamination may be overestimated (Ng et al., 2015).
61 According to Fernández-Caliani et al. (2019) the effects caused by PTEs on human health depend not only
62 on the exposure concentration but also on the intake rate and the biologically available fraction of
63 contaminants, and thus it is necessarily knowing the site-specific relative bioaccessibility (RBA) of the PTEs
64 of soils.

65 The metals and metalloids thus generated may come into contact with humans through different
66 exposure routes such as oral intake, inhalation or dermal absorption, the first being the one that generates
67 the greatest risk, particularly in children when exposed to ingestion of objects or food products that

68 contain metals (Broadway et al., 2010; Turner, 2011). For these reasons, risks arising from exposure to
69 specific chemicals from a standardized set of conditions are established by the United State Environmental
70 Protection Agency (USEPA, 1989; 2001; 2002), for different soil uses. These conditions combine chemical
71 toxicity data with the parameters defined for alleged uses of soils and the future of the exposure
72 scenarios, including the characteristics of the receivers and possible exposure routes. In fact, Schewald et
73 al. (2001) assured that the major control of toxicological effects is exercised by the fraction of soil that is
74 solubilized in the stomach and then available for absorption. This situation occurs very frequently and
75 sometimes it usually goes unnoticed according to studies carried out by some authors (Zia et al., 2011; Lu
76 et al., 2011), and it is proved that children were facing relatively higher health risks than adults, due to
77 the children crawl on the surface and have high dermal contact and they directly intake polluted soil
78 (Adimalla and Wang, 2018). Very different techniques have been recently developed for bioaccessibility
79 study of PTEs that simulate the physiological conditions in humans during the digestive process, called *in*
80 *vitro* extraction techniques (Bosso and Enzweiler, 2008; Pelfrène et al., 2011; Mateo et al., 2011). These
81 are synthetic gastric solution that recreate the biological processes and allow to estimate the oral
82 bioaccessibility (BAC) as the potential fraction of the toxic agent soluble in these conditions and then
83 available for absorption (Ruby et al., 1999; Morman et al., 2009). The importance of having a better
84 understanding about the bioaccessibility of pollutants is becoming increasingly important as a tool for the
85 evaluation of contaminated sites, which facilitates the establishment of more appropriate management
86 policies (Latawiec et al., 2010; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019). An important limitation of the method is
87 the possibility of obtaining inaccurate results because the bioaccessibility can be influenced by the
88 experimental conditions, the nature of the contaminant and the complexity of the sample (Okorie et al.,
89 2011). Even so, its application is valid as a simple, fast, reliable and inexpensive tool (Fernández-Caliani et
90 al., 2019).

91 Based on these premises the main objectives of this work were: (1) to evaluate the quality of Huelva
92 Township topsoils applying the generic reference levels proposed by Spanish legislation; (2) to calculate
93 the oral bioaccessibility degree of PTEs as an indicator of the relative bioavailability; (3) to study the
94 hazardousness of PTEs to citizens by conducting a human risk assessment analysis and (4) to evaluate the
95 use of sequential extraction procedures (SEP) as proxy methodologies to the oral bioaccessibility to
96 determine the bioaccessibility in specific sites.

97
98

99 **2. Materials and methods**

100

101 **2.1 Area of study**

102

103 The municipality of Huelva (Spain) is located at the confluence of the Tinto and Odiel rivers ("Estuary of
104 Huelva"), whose drainage basins rest mainly on Paleozoic materials from a Sedimentary Volcanic Complex,
105 which houses one of the largest massive sulphide deposits of the planet (Nieto et al., 2007), known as the
106 Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB). The weathering of the mineralization associated with the mining activity has
107 caused an ancestral contamination in the sediments of the Tinto and Odiel estuaries, making it one of the
108 most polluted in the world (e.g. Nieto et al., 2007; Sarmiento et al., 2009; Delgado et al., 2009; 2012). In
109 addition, this contamination has also strongly affected the surrounding soils, which are already affected
110 by the productive activity of two important industrial complexes (fertilizers and copper smelters) that
111 dump toxic waste that can be considered high risk to human health (Fernandez-Caliani, 2012). For
112 example, inorganic acids, combustion residues of fossil fuels, detergents, residues of metallurgical
113 products, animal feed and fertilizers could be a source of PTEs in the study area (Guillén et al., 2012). Also,
114 periurban areas surrounding Huelva are subject to severe anthropogenic pressure because of recent
115 urbanization. This fact could incorporate any soils with loss quality to the residential-living areas,
116 magnifying the human risk exposure. In addition, some of these potential discharges are produced as
117 atmospheric emissions and subsequently transported to the surrounding soils (Querol et al., 2002).
118 Summarizing the sources of contamination in the study area include acid mine drainage (AMD), urban
119 waste and agricultural activities.

120

121 **2.2 Sampling and physical treatment**

122

123 During the fall of 2007, 24 topsoil samples were collected at a depth between 0-15 cm from an area of
124 around 147 km² using a grid of 0.5 × 0.5 km in urban areas and a grid of 1.0 × 1.0 km in peri-urban areas
125 (Fig. 1). The collection included parks, open spaces, salt marshes, agricultural lands and industrial areas.
126 Two were related to agricultural activity, 7 to marsh areas, 9 corresponded to sites close to industrial
127 activities and 6 samples were taken in urban areas. All samples were processed according to the protocol
128 described by Salminen et al. (2005). Each sample was dried in an oven at 40 °C to avoid loss of volatiles, it
129 was fragmented using a wooden roller and then sieved through a 2 mm mesh, homogenized, milled at 63
130 μm and refrigerated (4 °C) in a polypropylene container until analysis. Although in the studies of PTEs the

131 most studied fraction corresponds to 250 μm , in our case the fraction of 63 μm was selected in order to
132 ensure a good released of Fe/Mn oxides and hydroxides, which could have an important role in the
133 behaviour of the PTEs in the study area (López-González et al., 2006; Guillén et al., 2011).

134 A number of selected samples were evaluated in 2011 by the *in vitro* extraction technique and analysed
135 for As, Cd, Co, Cr, Ni, Cu, Pb and Zn by ICP-MS determination. The details of the *in vitro* extraction
136 procedure and the analytical techniques can be seen in section 2.3.3. Because there are few studies on
137 the application of the *in vitro* extraction method in non-contaminated soils, in this work non-
138 contaminated sites were selected with the objective of evaluating and verifying the implementation of
139 this method.

140

141 **2.3 In vitro extraction procedure and quality control**

142

143 Synthetic gastric fluid was made by the addition of 100 ± 0.5 ml of a 0.4 M glycine buffer extraction agent
144 adjusted to pH 1.5 with *Suprapur* HCl (Merck). In 125 ml HDPE (high density polyethylene) containers, 100
145 ± 0.5 ml of a buffer extraction agent and 0.50 g (± 0.05) of the $<63 \mu\text{m}$ fraction were added. To guarantee
146 the quality of the solution, all the reagents used were of the highest purity available. The containers were
147 hermetically sealed to ensure that there is no loss of liquid when placed in an incubator with a water bath
148 at a temperature of 37 ± 0.2 °C with a rotation of 30 ± 2 rpm for 1 hour to perform the extraction process.
149 The containers were then removed, dried and placed on a surface to allow suspended particles to settle
150 to the bottom of the container. The containers were then removed, dried and placed on a surface to allow
151 the soil particles to settle to the bottom. A 15 ml aliquot of the supernatant was removed directly from
152 the bottles with a 20 ml Luer-Lok syringe and filtered through a 0.45 μm cellulose acetate filter (25 mm
153 diameter) to remove any particles. If the total time of the process exceeded 90 minutes, the test was
154 repeated because the stability of the samples could be compromised (Drexler, 2007). During the
155 experiment, the pH remained within 1.5 ± 0.5 and was adjusted manually at different time intervals. After
156 7 days, the samples were removed from the incubator rotor and stored at 4 °C until analysis.

157 The extracted solutions were analysed to determine the PTEs concentration by the Agilent 7500ce ICP-
158 MS emission spectrometry model (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with an octopolar
159 collision cell. To verify the accuracy of the analysis, blind triplicates were performed. Almost 5% of the
160 samples were analysed in triplicate using internal and external controls. Table 1 shows the recovery % (Eq.
161 1) obtained from the certified reference material (CNS 301-04) for freshwater sediments. The

162 determination of the most appropriate mode of operation for each element/isotope and an assessment
163 of the accuracy and reproducibility were based on the analysis of the certified reference material.

164
165 **$Recovery (\%) = (Value\ Retrieved / Certified\ Value) \times 100$** **(1)**

166
167 The calculations revealed a good % of recovery (> 90%, Table 1) for all the elements and the average
168 recovery value for the elements studied was $98.5 \pm 5.2\%$, which indicates the reliability of the data.

169 In addition, to verify the quality of the analysis, the relative percentage difference (%RPD) for the samples
170 was calculated according to equation 2, where S = determined value of the samples, and D = value of the
171 duplicates. Almost 5% of the samples were analysed in duplicate using internal and external controls. The
172 precision error (percentage difference relative RPD) was estimated at 0.75%, which denotes a high
173 confidence in the results.

174
175 **$RPD (\%) = (S - D) / (S + D) / 2 \times 100$** **(2)**

176
177 The pseudototal metal-metalloids content of each sample was analysed following the BCR sequential
178 extraction procedure using the improved four-step scheme described by Rauret et al. (1999). Details of
179 the scheme, quality control and results can be seen in Guillén et al. (2012).

180 181 **2.4 Bioaccessibility calculation**

182
183 The in vitro bioaccessibility (IVBA) was determined according to the methodology proposed by Okorie et
184 al. (2011) using equation 3, where C_{BAC} corresponds to the released concentration ($mg \cdot kg^{-1}$) of PTEs from
185 in vitro extraction with glycine, and $C_{pseudototal}$ is the released concentration ($mg \cdot kg^{-1}$) of PTEs according to
186 the BCR -SEP.

187
188 **$IVBA (\%) = (C_{BAC} / C_{pseudototal}) \times 100$** **(3)**

189
190 According to the literature, the sum of the first three steps of SEP corresponds to the total content related
191 to the potentially mobile fraction (%MF) and could represent the available fraction of each sample (Pérez
192 et al., 2008; Delgado et al., 2012). The distribution of contaminant elements in the different phases of the
193 modified BCR procedure gives an indication of its availability, which allows to assess the risks associated

194 to the environment (Lu et al., 2007). In this line, F1 of SEP, traditionally so-called Risk Assessment Code
195 (RAC) has frequently been used in previous investigations of contamination by heavy metals to assess the
196 potential ecological risk (i.e. Perin et al., 1985; Delgado et al., 2011). In order to compare the
197 methodological approaches, the exchangeable fraction (including carbonates) obtained by the fraction F1
198 of the BCR extraction (Guillén et al., 2012) was used to calculate %EF as follows ($F1/C_{\text{pseudototal}} \times 100$).

199

200 **2.5. Bioaccessibility geostatistical analysis by WISH**

201

202 The geostatistical mapping was done using the WISH program (Windows Interpretation System for the
203 Hydrogeologist), which is a hybrid between a CAD (computer-aided design system), a Geographic
204 Information System (GIS) and a chemical analysis package. The spatial distribution of the acquired results
205 of %EF, %MF and the pseudototal concentration of the BCR, as well as BAC of each element analysed in
206 this study were traced. The EF/BAC graphical operation was so performed with WISH. This relationship
207 was used to determine the differences between F1 (traditional risk assessment) and BAC in the study area
208 and, therefore, the precision of using F1 as BAC.

209 The spatial information of the sampling points, the topography and the geology were used together with
210 the results of the analysis of the experiments carried out to compile the conceptual model.

211 The results were imported into WISH using a simple search method with a radius of 5000, the minimum
212 point sector was 1, maximum 5, the maximum empty sector was 3, and the quadratic distance was used
213 to statistically represent the results.

214

215 **2.6 Health risk assessment**

216

217 ***2.6.1 Exposure scenarios***

218

219 To estimate the risk posed to human caused by pollution, a health risk assessment model has been
220 developed. According to Adimalla et al. (2019) human on-site exposure in urban -periurban soils is
221 conditioned by three main pathways including direct oral ingestion, dermal absorption and inhalation
222 (mouth and nose) of resuspended particles (Adimalla and Wang 2018; Chen et al. 2017; Deng et al. 2019;
223 USEPA 1989; Xu et al. 2018). The chronic daily dose (CDD: mg/kg-day) of potentially toxic elements
224 received through outdoor incidental soil ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation were calculated using
225 the formulation below (USEPA 1989; 2002):

226

$$227 \quad CDD_{ingestion} = \frac{C \times IR_{ing} \times ED \times EF}{BW \times AT} \times CF \quad (4)$$

$$228 \quad CDD_{inhalation} = \frac{C \times IR_{inh} \times ED \times EF}{BW \times AT \times PEF} \quad (5)$$

$$229 \quad CDD_{dermal} = \frac{C \times SA \times SAF \times DAF \times ED \times EF}{BW \times AT} \times CF \quad (6)$$

230

231 Were *C* is the PTEs soil concentration (mg/kg); ED is the exposure duration (years); EF is the exposure
 232 frequency (days/year); BW is the body weight of the exposed individual (kg); *IR_{ing}*, the ingestion rate, *IR_{inh}*
 233 the inhalation rate; AT is the time period over which the exposure is averaged (days); SA is the exposed
 234 skin surface area (cm²); AF is a skin-soil adherence factor (mg/cm²); DAF is the soil dermal absorption
 235 factor or dermal bioavailability (unitless); and CF is an units conversion factor (kg/mg). The parameters
 236 and factor used for the model have been listed in Table 2.

237

238 **2.6.2 Non-carcinogenic risk assessment**

239 The non-carcinogenic risk was estimated using the hazard quotient (HQ) as the ratio between chronic
 240 daily dose (CDD) and the reference dose (RfD) reported by USEPA (1989). According to this guideline HQ_{*i*}
 241 is the hazard quotient for an individual element (unitless), As, Co, Cu and Pb in this study; CDD_{*i*} is the daily
 242 dose (mg/kg-day); and RfD_{*i*} is the chronic reference dose or acceptable intake level (mg/kg-day) as can be
 243 seen in the following equations, and therefore HI (Hazard Index) is the sum of individualized HQ .

244

$$245 \quad HQ = \frac{CDD}{RfD} \quad (7)$$

$$246 \quad HI = \sum \frac{CDD_i}{RfD_i} \quad (8)$$

247

248 According to USEPA (1989), if the HI value is smaller than 1, no risk of non-carcinogenic effects is supposed
 249 to occur, when HI value exceeds 1, potential non-carcinogenic adverse effects could appear on humans
 250 (USEPA 1989).

251

252

253

254

255

256 **2.6.3 Carcinogenic risk assessment**

257

258 The carcinogenic health risk values for oral, inhalation and dermal exposure to As and Pb over a 70 years
259 lifetime (Chen et al., 2015; Deng et al., 2019; Zhaoyong et al., 2019) were estimated using the following
260 method proposed by USEPA (1989; 2002):

261

262 $CR = CDD \times SF$ (9)

263 $TCR = \sum CR$ (10)

264

265 where CRi is the carcinogenic risk for an individual element; CDD is the chronic daily dose averaged over
266 a 70-year lifetime; TCR is the total carcinogenic risk; SF is the slope factor (mg/kg/day) as listed in Table 3.
267 According to USEPA guideline, the cancerogenic risk for adult and child residents is additive using the
268 assumption that an individual will live at the affected site from childhood until an age of 30 years (Adimalla
269 et al., 2019). The CR and TCR values less than 1.0E-06 are proposed as negligible, whereas values
270 exceeding 1.0E-04 are considered harmful to human health (USEPA, 1989). However, the European legal
271 framework and Spanish legislation consider 1.0E-05 as the threshold value for human health risk
272 (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

273

274 **3. Results and discussion**

275

276 **3.1. Trace elements pseudototal concentration**

277

278 The soils of Huelva Township present high concentrations of PTEs frequently derived from industrial and
279 mining activities (Table 4). Pseudototal median concentration of As, Cu, Pb and Zn were respectively 181,
280 988, 288 and 781 mg·kg⁻¹, values near the anomalous soil concentrations found in the surrounding
281 industrial areas (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2012). Furthermore, these results are well beyond the regional
282 geochemical background and the local soil concentrations established by Galán et al. (2008) and Guillén
283 et al. (2012), respectively. Taking into account the specific-site parameters, there exists a strong
284 correlation between the maximum concentration of the PTEs and the land use (Table 4). In this sense,
285 variation of standard deviations of As, Cu, Pb and Zn indicated that the concentration of these heavy
286 metals greatly varied among different sampling sites.

287 Generally, median concentrations of As and Pb, and to a lesser extent Cu, exceeded the health-based
288 screening levels (GRL) for the different land uses (Junta de Andalucía, 2015). GRL were also overpassed by
289 Co in samples 76, 91, 107, 136, 163, 182 and 184. Hence, according to the regulatory normative, As, Co,
290 Cu and Pb concentrations could suppose a potential human risk, and these soils should be declared as
291 potentially contaminated (Junta de Andalucía, 2015), requiring a site-specific quantitative risk assessment
292 (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019). In addition, when PTEs concentration overpass 100 times the refence
293 values this soil is considered extremely polluted, and thus, should be immediately emended (Junta de
294 Andalucía, 2015). Samples 76* (As, Pb), 90 and 107 (As), 136* (As, Cu) and 97 (As) did not break this
295 threshold for any of the PTEs, but they ten-fold overpassed the limit and therefore suppose a considerable
296 human risk. On the other hand, the reference level is certainly not surpassed by samples 43 and 144 and
297 therefore the risk should be considered low and detailed health risk studies are not required for these
298 soils.

299 Other elements like Cd, Cr and Ni showed concentrations around or even lower to the local background
300 level and could be considered as natural origin. This trend has been similarly described by other authors
301 such as López-González et al. (2006) and Morillo et al. (2008) in studies of SW Iberian coastal areas and
302 Guillén et al. (2012) at the specific study area. Although the concentration of Zn was higher than both the
303 regional and local background, it was not considered for specific risk analyses according to the risk
304 criterium, since it never overpassed the GRL (Junta de Andalucía, 2015).

305

306 **3.2. Bioaccessibility of potential toxic elements**

307

308 The results obtained from the simple *in vitro* extraction procedure (bioaccessibility; %IVBAC) are shown
309 in Table S1 (Supplementary data). Recent studies have indicated that an overestimation could be
310 produced using simple methods to estimate bioaccessibility (Fernández- Caliani et al., 2019). However,
311 this study also reveals that the extractable concentration in the gastric phase did not significantly varied
312 when the intestinal phase was added. Particularly, Pb and Zn bioaccessibility decreased due to re-
313 adsorption or complexation processes under the alkaline intestinal conditions. Also, as Rodrigues et al.
314 (2018) found, the extraction efficiency of simple and UBM (Unified BARGE Method, Wragg et al., 2011)
315 methods is statistically similar, supporting the use of these methods. In fact, Schewald et al. (2001) assured
316 that the major control of toxicological effects is exercised by the solubilized fraction of soil in the stomach
317 and then available for absorption. According to Fernández- Caliani et al. (2019) most of the PTEs were
318 preferentially extracted in the gastric phase.

319 The plotted results (Fig. 2) of these calculations correspond to the median value (50% of Tukey's box
320 diagrams). The range of variation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) of PTEs extracted from the potential IBVA was: As (2.1 - 697),
321 Cd (0.14 - 15.1), Co (1.70 - 86.1), Cr (1.44 - 78.4), Cu (57.9 - 9321), Ni (1.30 - 24.2), Pb (21.9 - 1500) and Zn
322 (26.1 - 2241 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). The standard deviations of As, Cu, Pb and Zn showed very high values denoting these
323 elements with the highest degree of dispersion in contrast to Cd and Ni. Based on %IVBA the elements
324 can be sorted in descending order as follows: Cd (65%) > Zn (54%) > Pb (46%) > Co (38%) = As (38%) = Cu
325 (34%) > Cr (26%) > Ni (20%). The %IVBA was always higher than the calculated %EF (Fig. 2), higher than
326 the first two phases (F1 + F2) of the SEP for Ni, Cu, Pb and Zn and, even more, higher than %MF (F1 + F2 +
327 F3) in the case of As, Cd, Co and Cr. Some authors (Poggio et al., 2009; Okorie et al., 2011; Sialelli et al.,
328 2010; 2011) successfully supported the existence of a good linear correlation (R^2) between the
329 pseudototal content and the bioaccessible fraction, which offers the possibility of using pseudototal as a
330 statistically reliable indicator to predict BAC. However, according to a study of metals bioaccessibility in
331 household dust reported by Turner (2011), this parameter could be largely influenced by changes in the
332 physicochemical conditions during *in vitro* extraction. In our work a good correlation (examples for As and
333 Cu in Fig. 3) was found between the pseudototal content and the IVBA.

334

335 **3.3. Spatial distribution and related geological-anthropic framework**

336

337 The results of the *in vitro* digestion plotted by WISH are showed in Fig. 4. The southern of Huelva township
338 has been determined as the area with the highest risk for the human health, corresponding geologically
339 with the saltmarshes (quaternary materials). The surrounding areas of the Odiel River present the highest
340 BAC of Pb and As, probably derived from the old mining industry described in Guillén et al. (2011). The
341 primary materials were carried from the IPB to be processed in the industrial complex "Punta del Sebo",
342 and thus occasionally during the transport process uncontrolled releases could occurred. Cd, Co, Cr, Cu,
343 Ni and Zn are clearly related to the Punta del Sebo industrial Complex. High IVBA levels of Zn were also
344 detected in the industrial Complexes of "Tejar-Colmenilla" and "El Rincón". Similarly, Cu was also detected
345 in the Tartessos industrial Complex (Fig. 4a). In fact, the most recent studies about environmental risk
346 assessments suggest the existence of a high ecological risk in the area, which decreases from the
347 surrounding industrial estates to the city (Guillén et al., 2011; Fernández-Caliani, 2012).

348 Several authors (i.e. Perin et al., 1985; Delgado et al., 2011) have used F1 as an approach to potentially
349 "bio"-available fraction. Fig. 4b depicts that the quotient F1/IVBA show values below the unit in the study
350 area for all the elements, except at the old mineral port for Cu, Ni and Zn, suggesting a higher extraction

351 capability by the BCR-F1 (eight-fold higher for Cu and Zn). This could be due to the presence of solid wastes
352 from the polymetallic sulphides exploited in the IBP, previously reported by Guillén et al. (2012), that
353 arrived at the ore port, and were frequently used as ballast bed for the train tracks. Also, the location of
354 the city of Huelva at the confluence of Tinto and Odiel rivers, one of the most polluted river-system in the
355 world receiving higher metal fluxes associated with the mining activity (Nieto et al., 2007), has led to the
356 contamination of the estuarine sediments (i.e. López-González et al., 2006). Preliminary, it could be
357 assumed that soils of this area present easy soluble Cu, Ni and Zn rich minerals. However, as it has been
358 previously reported, the highest IVBA values of As and Pb were obtained in this location, indicating that
359 the traditional approach of EF% to BAC% could conduct to false interpretations and to underestimate the
360 associated risk, while to overestimation of the associated risk of Cu, Ni and Zn, that showed higher EF% in
361 the sites.

362 On the other hand, it is evident that Cr, Ni, Co and Zn showed better mean correlations between MF%
363 and IVBA% than the rest of the analysed elements. Specifically, these elements showed a clear spatial
364 correlation with the gray-blue marlstone unit (Guillén et al., 2012), mainly representing lithological inputs
365 from soil and bedrock erosion of the basins in the SW of Iberian Peninsula (López-González et al., 2006;
366 Delgado et al., 2012).

367

368 **3.4. Relative bioavailability adjusted**

369

370 The equations used to determine the chronic daily doses assume 100% bioavailability of the ingested soil-
371 borne contaminant, but soil conditions such as pH, texture, and organic matter, define the metal
372 speciation and thus their bioavailability (Harichandan et al., 2013; Darko et al., 2017). Hence, to reduce
373 the uncertainty in quantitative risk assessment, the site-specific bioaccessibility estimated from the gastric
374 extraction has been incorporated in our risk analysis, since it could be considered as the fraction of the
375 PTEs when an individual is exposed upon soil ingestion (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019). This fraction,
376 according to recent studies (Caboche, 2009; Roussel et al., 2010; Pelfrêne et al., 2011), can be used to
377 predict the relative bioavailability (RBA) from measurements of IVBA applying an in vivo - in vitro lineal
378 correlation model. The site-specific bioavailability of potential PTEs, was predicted according to the
379 following equations and the results can be seen in the table S1.

380

$$381 \quad IVBA_{As} (\%) = 1,00 * RBA - 0,01 \quad R^2 = 0,98 \text{ (Caboche, 2009)} \quad (14)$$

$$382 \quad IVBA_{Pb} (\%) = 1,10 * RBA + 1,86 \quad R^2 = 0,93 \text{ (Caboche, 2009)} \quad (15)$$

383 This adjusted RBA values were incorporated in order to reduce the uncertainty in the cancer risk analysis
384 of potential carcinogenic effects of As and Pb, and thus the cancer risk was adjusted ($CR_{adjusted}$) following
385 the procedure described by Fernández-Caliani et al. (2019) where RBA is the predicted relative
386 bioavailability adjustment factor (unitless):

387

$$388 \quad CR_{adjusted} = CDD \times SF \times RBA \quad (16)$$

389

390 Similarly, the non-carcinogenic effects of the potential PTEs evolving in our analysis has been corrected
391 by adjusting the hazard quotient (HQ) as follows:

392

$$393 \quad HQ_{adjusted} = \frac{CDD}{RfD} \times RBA \quad (17)$$

394

395 To continue the same procedure, considering the non-carcinogenic exposure of the soil as the sum of
396 several PTEs (equation 8), when the individual HQ_i adjustment by RBA is not possible, the default value
397 (100% bioavailability or IVBA%) was used to correct pseudototal concentration estimating the potential
398 health risk of the soils.

399

400 **3.5. Human exposure assessment and risk health**

401

402 Human exposure to metal contaminants in urban topsoils can occur through ingestion, dermal contact,
403 and inhalation. In this context accidental soil ingestion is often the most important risk pathway (Ng et al.
404 2015; Darko et al., 2017). Since the selected residential area offers very limited space to plant-garden,
405 ingestion of home-grown products is not considered for this site (Asante-Duah, 2012). Considering that
406 main family living in the Huelva urban and peri-urban area includes both adults and children the risk
407 assessment was therefore conducted separately for As, Co, Cu and Pb. Among population, children are
408 considered the most sensitive receptors due to the greater tendency for hand-to-mouth contact, which
409 may facilitate incidental soil ingestion (Basta and Juhasz, 2014). Therefore, in the residential or
410 recreational areas the risk assessment was determined for both adults and children, but in other sites
411 (including industrial sector) the risk study was only applied for adults.

412 The calculated HI and TCR that incorporated bioaccessibility adjustment are given in tables 2S and 3S for
413 adults and children, respectively. Since Cd, Cr, Ni and Zn concentrations in the soil samples were below
414 the applicable GRL established by autonomous government, and the concentrations in most of the IVBA

415 extracts were in general low, the risk associated with accidental exposure of soils contaminated with those
416 elements were deemed fairly low and therefore excluded from the risk characterization. In fact, Co was
417 studied since it overpassed the GRL in the samples 76, 91, 107, 136, 163, 182 and 184, but they did not
418 contribute significant to the total non-carcinogenic risk of these sites (supplementary data), which
419 ranged between three and four order of magnitude below the limit proposed by the normative.
420 According to these three potential pathway exposures, the order of the hazard quotients (HQ) for the
421 metals analysed were $As > Pb > Cu > Co$, showing As and Pb one and three order of magnitude over Cu
422 and Co, respectively (Tables S2, S3). Thus, for on-site incidental soil exposure pathways As and Pb were
423 the main contributors to the overall risks, as other recent studies of soil risk assessment have highlighted
424 (i.e. Darko et al., 2017; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019). Also, a study conducted to industrial soil in
425 periurban areas of Huelva, concluded that the main pollutants are As and Pb (Fernández-Caliani, 2012).
426 In fact, the total non-carcinogenic hazard index (HI), that largely varied by the sample sites, ranged
427 between 0,04 (sample 43) and 4,67 (sample 76*) for adults, with a mean value below the threshold value.
428 However, analysing the individual HI for the specific-site (Fig. 5), the risk limit was exceeded in the
429 industrial samples (97, 134), urban/recreational areas (76*, 135* and 136*) and in the less extents in the
430 peri-urban areas with other land uses (samples 90, 107). HI varied between 0,31(sample 184) and 32,3
431 (sample 76*) for children, with a mean of 6,11, overpassing the acceptable level for practically all samples.
432 Extremely high values (around 10) were found in the sites destined to recreational areas surrounding
433 Huelva city (76*, 135* and 136*) revealing the adverse effect that the PTEs would pose for children health.
434 The TCR for adults varied between $6,43E-05$ and $1,97E-06$ for As and between $1,45E-05$ and $2,67E-07$ for
435 Pb, with mean values of $1,19E-04$ and $1,98E-06$, respectively, whereas that for children ranged between
436 $8,97E-04$ and $2,74E-06$ for As and between $9,36E-06$ and $1,76E-07$ for Pb, with mean values of $1,66E-04$
437 and $1,55E-06$, respectively. Thus, the average cancer risks in the studied soils were unacceptable for As
438 and negligible for Pb based on regulatory normative. In detail, the adults TCR_{As} overpassed the threshold
439 values at all samples except the sites 7, 184 and 219 (Fig. 6a), showing the extremely high value associated
440 to the old mineral port (Guillén et al., 2012) in sample 76*. In contrast, the TRC_{Pb} only overpassed the limit
441 in this sample. To asses a realist scenario, the TCR for children will be only described for samples included
442 in figure 6b, since a child chance of developing cancer in a lifetime by incidental oral exposure in industrial
443 and/or other soil use areas should be extremely low. Nevertheless, As may pose health risks to children
444 living and playing at any soil located in the urban or periurban recreational areas (Fig. 6b), involving a
445 concern according to this assessment model. In this context, the risk for Pb was below limit at all samples.

446 It should be noted that if the hazard quotients and carcinogenic risks are determined using the total metal
447 content without adjustment, the resulting values for both children and adult receptors would be
448 overestimated. In fact, our data showed TRC_{Pb} values two times higher than the acceptable level and TRC_{As}
449 more than three times higher, while HI ranged around 3,5 times higher than HI adjusted for As, Co, Cu
450 and Pb. This data highlights the importance of the use of bioaccessibility for the risk characterization
451 (Darko et al., 2017; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

452 Overall, the hazard quotients and total carcinogenic risk data indicated that children are more vulnerable
453 to the contaminants than adults, as was described by other studies about human risk in urban soils (Darko
454 et al., 2017; Adimalla et al., 2019). Also, the reported soil exceeding the regulatory threshold should be
455 classified as polluted and, therefore, decontaminated to prevent the human risk exposure.

456

457 **Final remarks**

458

459 Spatial analysis of WISH has revealed that significative differences can be found between exchangeable
460 fraction (F1-SEP) and de IVBA, which could conduct to false interpretations and underestimate the risk for
461 As and Pb, but overestimation the risk for other PTEs like Cu, Ni and Zn, when the traditional approach to
462 determine the BAC fraction is applied in risk analyses. These results confirm that the potential risk of PTEs
463 in the soils for human health should not be evaluated exclusively according to their concentration (total
464 or partial).

465 Total concentration of PTEs in all urban and periurban soils of Huelva township have overpassed the
466 regulatory level to declare a soil under risk analyses in at least one element, except the specific-sites 43
467 and 144.

468 Although, the bioaccessibility in soils of the study area were largely related to their pseudototal
469 concentrations, elemental bioaccessibility was variable with As and Pb having the highest bioaccessibility
470 mainly associated to sites where higher PTEs concentration were found. However, the adjustment of the
471 daily intake using site-specific oral bioaccessibility/bioavailability data provided a more accurate
472 estimation of the human health risks from exposure estimation, reducing uncertainty probably derived
473 from soil characteristics.

474 The results of the risk analysis based on the USEPA's criteria, after RBA-adjusted exposure assessment,
475 suggest that the contribution of ingestion pathway is much higher than the inhalation and dermal contacts
476 in the Huelva township for children and adults. Hazard index (HI) values are higher than the recommended
477 limit (HI=1) for children and adults. As and Pb are the main contributor to the overall risk, suggesting that

478 these metals have an unacceptable non-carcinogenic risk for residents. TCR (total carcinogenic risk)
479 overpass the regulatory threshold (1E-05) in numerous specific-sites both for adults and children, showing
480 an extremely risk at site 76 (“greenway” periurban recreational area).

481 Finally, the hazard quotients and total carcinogenic risk data indicated that children are more vulnerable
482 to the contaminants in urban and periurban areas, of which, recreational areas surrounding city posed
483 more elevated risk. Also, the reported soil exceeding the regulatory threshold should be classified as
484 polluted and, therefore, applying the corrective methods to prevent the human risk exposure,
485 concentrating mitigation strategies to reduce mainly the As concentration to acceptable limits.

486

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488

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492

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Figures

Fig. 1.- Map of the study area showing the location of the sampling sites and the geological setting.

Fig. 2.- Boxplots of IVAB and EF (both in %) for As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Pb and Zn obtained from Huelva township soils, showing minimum, maximum, first quartile (Q1), median and third quartile (Q3).

Fig. 3.- Relationship IVAB (%) vs mobile fraction (MF) and pseudototal fraction both in mg/kg for As, as well as IVBA (%) vs pseudototal concentration (mg/kg) for Cu.

Fig. 4.- a) IVBA fraction (%) map obtained through geostatistical mapping using WISH; b) Map showing F1(SEP) / IVBA relation.

Fig. 5.- Hazard index adjusted by bioaccessibility and relative bioavailability (RBA) values for both adults and children in all samples of the study area. The regulatory limits are given for comparative purposes. * Indicates sites now converted into walkways and recreational areas.

Fig. 6.- Total carcinogenic risk values for As and Pb exposure adjusted by bioavailability (RBA) values showing the regulatory threshold proposed by autonomous government. a) TCR for adult in all specific-site of the study area; b) TCR for children only at living or recreational scenarios. * Indicates sites now converted into walkways and recreational areas.

Figure 1

Tables

Table 1.- Results obtained from *in vitro* extraction ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and quality control of the data showing % of recovery results of CRM (CNS 301-04), precision (%RPD) for all samples, and detection limits for elements under study.

Table 2.- Synthesis of the main exposure routes, information of parameters and factors used for the health risk assessment in urban soils (definitions and reference values).

Table 3.- Reference doses (RfD) for non-carcinogenic heavy metals and slope factors (SF) for carcinogenic metals.

Table 4.- Trace element concentrations ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) of all samples analysed showing land uses. Local background, regional baseline concentrations and Andalusian regulatory levels (GRL) are also given for comparative purposes.

Samples	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7	2,13	0,14	1,99	2,33	99,8	1,58	38,2	75,7
43	3,61	0,19	4,18	6,92	64,9	3,40	21,9	26,1
76	697	0,64	12,7	2,26	58,0	2,30	1500	258
77	110	0,05	6,82	4,25	270	4,36	171	168
90	290	0,61	6,80	14,1	316	4,36	124	242
91	111	1,77	29,3	5,69	1037	14,7	113	933
97	410	0,45	4,09	39,7	312	3,76	299	595
107	214	0,78	86,1	17,2	1639	24,2	366	2241
117	55,5	2,03	9,88	1,83	163	3,45	84,9	1204
121	136	0,10	2,79	11,4	258	1,49	83,6	183
124	53,0	0,78	6,73	1,44	2631	3,35	31,5	384
134	89,7	15,1	2,95	34,7	7291	3,34	377	942
135	174	1,70	2,76	4,69	249	1,41	376	203
136	239	14,3	7,15	78,4	9321	5,44	767	1396
144	5,57	0,48	2,71	5,39	484	5,77	60,6	732
145	50,1	1,92	5,58	9,14	475	2,53	120	479
146	38,2	4,22	6,27	19,8	341	3,45	204	1011
149	79,5	0,94	7,23	3,72	251	2,61	112	136
160	26,2	1,50	6,55	2,85	458	2,35	143	430
163	13,8	1,00	5,78	3,74	378	4,80	73,9	266
182	15,7	1,55	13,9	11,4	171	3,01	162	1615
184	2,62	0,04	1,70	12,3	223	1,34	28,2	191
190	17,3	0,61	4,14	5,00	113	2,15	129	328
219	10,0	0,09	2,43	5,36	224	1,30	71,6	66,7
Max	697	15,1	86,1	78,4	9321	24,2	1500	2241
Min	2,13	0,04	1,70	1,44	57,96	1,30	21,93	26,08
Mean	142	2,64	13,06	15,28	1446	5,22	278	654
SD	162	3,98	17,2	17,1	2306	4,99	318	569
d.l. (μgL^{-1})	3,05	2.846×10^{-1}	3.356×10^{-2}	6,640	4.943×10^{-1}	1070	7.568×10^{-2}	1,22
CNS 301-04*	14,7	33,0	25,5	32,9	41,9	30,8	92,4	96,3
%Recovery	98,7	106	102	95,2	105	93,9	92,7	94,7
%RPD	0,6	0,1	0,4	2,1	0,9	0,5	0,5	0,9

d.l. = Detection Limit; SD = Standard deviation; %RPD = Relative percentage difference

*Trace elements on fresh water sediment: CRM CNS 301-04 (certified reference material)

Soil exposure pathways: Oral ingestion, Inhalation ingestion, Skin contact

	Exposure parameters	Units	Receptor (on-site)		Source
			Adult	Child	
AT	Averaging time carcinogens 70x365	years		25550	(Adimalla, 2019; USEPA, 2002)
	Non-carcinogens EDx365	years	10950	2190	
BW	Body weight	kg	70	20	(Narsimha and Rajitha, 2019)
ED	Exposure duration	years	30	6	USEPA (2002)
EF	Exposure frequency	days/year		365	USEPA (2002)
IR_{ing}	Ingestion rate of soil	mg/day	100	200	USEPA (1989, 2002)
IR_{inh}	Inhalation rate of soil	m ³ /day	15	5	(Adimalla, 2019)
SA	Exposed skin surface area	cm ²	4350	1600	USEPA (2002)
SAF	Skin adherence factor	mg/cm ²	0,7	0,2	USEPA (2002)
DAF	Soil dermal absorption factor				—
	For arsenic	unitless	0,03	0,001*	Fernández-Caliani et al. (2019)
	For other trace elements	unitless	0,1	0,001*	* Adimalla (2019)
PEF	Particle emission factor	m ³ /kg		1,36E+09	(Chen et al., 2017; USEPA, 2002)
CF	Conversion factor	kg/mg		1,00E-06	USEPA (2002)

Metal	Reference dose RfD (mg/kg/day)			Slope factor SF (unitless)		
	RfD _{ing}	RfD _{inh}	RfD _{dermal}	SF _{ing}	SF _{inh}	SF _{dermal}
As	3,00E-04	1,23E-04	1,23E-04	1,50E+00	4,30E-03	3,66E+00
Cd	1,00E-03	1,00E-03	2,50E-05	—	6,30E+00	—
Co	0,03*	3,00E-02	3,00E-02	3,00E-02	3,00E-02	3,00E-02
Cr	3,00E-03	2,86E-03	3,00E-03	5,01E-01	4,20E+01	2,00E+01
Cu	4,00E-02	4,00E-02	1,20E-02	—	—	—
Ni	2,00E-02	2,06E-02	5,40E-03	1,70E+00	—	4,25E+01
Pb	1,40E-03	3,52E-03	5,24E-04	0,0085**	—	—
Zn	3,00E-01	3,00E-01	6,00E-02	—	—	—

* Finley et al. (2012); ** Cocârță et al. (2016), Adimalla (2019); ***mg/m³

Element		As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
Sample	Use								
7	Other uses	8,90	0,42	5,40	24,2	1945	11,3	88,4	216
43	Other uses	10,6	0,27	8,60	40,0	386	20,1	68,6	74,6
76*	Other uses	2066	1,07	110	6,50	269	8,50	5469	414
77*	Other uses	212	0,28	18,6	33,1	734	26,4	306	522
90	Other uses	504	0,97	14,9	51,1	996	26,8	490	735
91	Urban	151	1,96	39,3	42,7	1180	40,7	190	1101
97	Industrial	701	1,07	13,2	86,9	1011	25,6	651	983
107	Other uses	417	1,18	124	51,0	1807	48,7	594	3513
117	Other uses	242	3,46	22,6	32,7	628	23,7	176	1857
121	Industrial	276	0,16	8,00	43,4	764	18,1	297	321
124	Industrial	218	1,21	19,1	25,5	4225	17,7	229	708
134	Industrial	200	15,9	18,0	61,4	>10000	12,5	611	1528
135*	Other uses	294	3,60	18,1	14,5	710	6,00	684	1346
136*	Other uses	370	18,4	38,7	112	>10000	37,7	1225	4011
144	Industrial	17,1	0,52	5,40	31,8	2003	22,4	83,6	1049
145*	Other uses	126	2,37	8,60	16,3	1053	7,50	403	583
146*	Other uses	109	4,74	17,4	49,0	1890	19,9	282	1306
149	Urban	201	1,26	17,2	37,8	748	24,0	188	545
160	Urban	162	1,67	12,8	22,7	967	10,6	261	605
163	Urban	69,2	1,18	37,7	49,4	980	12,7	254	2242
182	Industrial	67,6	2,32	45,1	55,2	1288	18,1	487	4707
184	Urban	22,6	0,30	13,1	40,3	623	16,9	97,0	497
190	Industrial	64,8	0,85	15,8	35,6	601	16,8	295	828
219	Urban	74,2	0,20	5,40	18,2	599	10,9	144	246
Pseudototal		181	1,18	17,3	38,9	988	18,1	288	781
Mean		274	2,72	26,5	40,9	1155	20,2	566	1247
Standard deviation		417	4,61	30,1	23,1	849	10,6	1077	1224
Reference values									
<i>Bkg</i>		8,45 ± 1,03	0,13 ± 0,02	9,72 ± 0,73	45,1 ± 6,80	17,6 ± 2,70	24,2 ± 2,30	26,8 ± 8,80	47,2 ± 2,40
<i>Regional baseline</i> ^a		25	-	19	95	32	35	38	76
<i>EPA GRL</i> ^b		-	3,41	1,80	11,4	34,1	22,7	-	34,1
Regulatory level ^c									
<i>Industrial</i>		40	750	250	10000	10000	10000	2750	10000
<i>Urban</i>		36	75	25	10000	3130	1530	275	10000
<i>Other uses</i>		36	25	24	10000	595	1530	275	10000

All values are expressed in mg·Kg⁻¹ / Bkg: Background ± standard deviation (Guillen et al., 2012) / Pseudototal = median concentration

* Areas, with other users assigned, where recreational areas ("greenway", parks, garden) have been enabled in recent time.

a (Galán et al., 2008); b (EPA, 2002); c (Junta de Andalucía, 2015)

[Click here to view linked References](#)

Sample	As				
	$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA	%RBA
7	6.77	8.90	2.13	23.91	23.92
43	8.89	10.60	3.61	34.04	34.05
76	58.18	2065.70	697.08	33.75	33.76
77	54.73	211.50	109.80	51.92	51.93
90	17.70	504.20	290.22	57.56	57.57
91	28.87	150.60	110.75	73.54	73.55
97	101.97	700.90	410.26	58.53	58.54
107	31.59	416.90	214.25	51.39	51.40
117	12.37	241.70	55.54	22.98	22.99
121	54.89	275.60	136.06	49.37	49.38
124	8.56	217.80	53.01	24.34	24.35
134	66.39	200.30	89.70	44.78	44.79
135	102.89	294.20	174.09	59.17	59.18
136	85.35	369.60	238.94	64.65	64.66
144	6.35	17.10	5.57	32.55	32.56
145	28.70	126.10	50.15	39.77	39.78
146	20.92	109.40	38.23	34.95	34.96
149	25.82	200.70	79.53	39.63	39.64
160	14.95	162.40	26.22	16.14	16.15
163	13.87	69.20	13.83	19.99	20.00
182	14.35	67.60	15.70	23.22	23.23
184	7.90	22.60	2.62	11.59	11.60
190	13.75	64.80	17.31	26.71	26.72
219	10.70	74.20	9.97	13.44	13.45
Max	102.89	2065.70	697.08	73.54	73.55
Min	6.35	8.90	2.13	11.59	11.60
Mean	33.19	274.28	118.52	37.83	37.84
SD	30.28	417.45	161.95	17.33	17.33

Cd				Co	
$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA	$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal
0.29	0.42	0.14	33.55	1.65	5.40
0.19	0.27	0.19	69.27	3.87	8.60
0.75	1.07	0.64	59.38	204.38	110.40
0.12	0.28	0.05	16.45	8.95	18.60
0.66	0.97	0.61	62.57	5.25	14.90
1.54	1.96	1.77	90.19	28.40	39.30
0.42	1.07	0.45	42.11	4.60	13.20
0.34	1.18	0.78	65.78	109.27	123.70
2.65	3.46	2.03	58.56	13.46	22.60
0.07	0.16	0.10	64.67	2.59	8.00
0.76	1.21	0.78	64.75	12.08	19.10
7.57	15.91	15.14	95.16	4.30	18.00
1.20	3.60	1.70	47.27	1.26	18.10
7.40	18.37	14.25	77.58	9.19	38.70
0.35	0.52	0.48	92.92	1.63	5.40
1.96	2.37	1.92	81.14	4.28	8.60
2.54	4.74	4.22	89.04	6.04	17.40
0.73	1.26	0.94	74.72	7.78	17.20
1.25	1.67	1.50	89.53	5.91	12.80
0.46	1.18	1.00	84.81	6.60	37.70
0.73	2.32	1.55	66.63	7.50	45.10
0.12	0.30	0.04	13.25	1.67	13.10
0.55	0.85	0.61	71.69	6.68	15.80
0.20	0.20	0.09	46.24	1.84	5.40
7.57	18.37	15.14	95.16	204.38	123.70
0.07	0.16	0.04	13.25	1.26	5.40
1.37	2.72	2.12	64.89	19.13	26.55
2.02	4.61	3.98	22.62	45.02	30.09

		Cr			
C_{BAC}	%IVBA	$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA
1.99	36.90	3.44	24.20	2.33	9.61
4.18	48.62	6.73	40.00	6.92	17.29
12.67	11.47	11.82	6.50	2.26	34.77
6.82	36.68	7.25	33.10	4.25	12.84
6.80	45.62	13.71	51.10	14.12	27.63
29.28	74.50	8.71	42.70	5.69	13.31
4.09	30.99	17.99	86.90	39.70	45.69
86.07	69.58	13.16	51.00	17.15	33.64
9.88	43.72	3.89	32.70	1.83	5.59
2.79	34.86	10.68	43.40	11.42	26.31
6.73	35.25	3.03	25.50	1.44	5.65
2.95	16.40	13.80	61.40	34.70	56.52
2.76	15.25	2.86	14.50	4.69	32.33
7.15	18.47	20.49	112.10	78.39	69.93
2.71	50.19	5.78	31.80	5.39	16.94
5.58	64.94	4.47	16.30	9.14	56.09
6.27	36.03	8.77	49.00	19.76	40.33
7.23	42.04	8.35	37.80	3.72	9.85
6.55	51.18	3.67	22.70	2.85	12.54
5.78	15.32	6.47	49.40	3.74	7.58
13.95	30.92	7.38	55.20	11.43	20.70
1.70	13.00	3.24	40.30	12.32	30.58
4.14	26.20	5.24	35.60	5.00	14.05
2.43	44.93	2.37	18.20	5.36	29.48
86.07	74.50	20.49	112.10	78.39	69.93
1.70	11.47	2.37	6.50	1.44	5.59
10.02	37.21	8.05	40.89	12.65	26.22
17.18	17.57	4.95	23.09	17.09	17.59

Cu				Ni	
$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA	$\Sigma F1+F2+F3$ BCR	Pseudototal
592.5	1945.02	99.83	5.13	2.50	11.30
37.7	386.46	64.90	16.79	6.79	20.10
2893.0	268.58	57.96	21.58	46.17	8.50
1016.7	733.79	269.68	36.75	9.01	26.40
681.2	996.44	315.94	31.71	6.51	26.80
961.1	1179.51	1037.13	87.93	20.59	40.70
616.1	1010.58	312.20	30.89	8.30	25.60
1533.4	1807.49	1638.68	90.66	24.19	48.70
446.5	628.08	162.52	25.87	6.60	23.70
457.7	763.89	257.52	33.71	3.41	18.10
4227.5	4225.43	2631.33	62.27	3.02	17.70
15638.4	10000.0	7290.82	72.91	0.00	12.50
414.7	709.88	249.04	35.08	0.76	6.00
17559.5	10000.0	9320.73	93.21	4.75	37.70
22.1	2003.06	484.31	24.18	4.78	22.40
973.2	1053.19	474.85	45.09	3.40	7.50
953.6	1889.51	341.43	18.07	4.42	19.90
610.5	748.32	250.74	33.51	5.69	24.00
650.3	966.51	458.49	47.44	3.44	10.60
44.4	979.95	377.92	38.57	2.57	12.70
186.8	1287.68	170.63	13.25	3.33	18.10
283.2	622.50	222.91	35.81	4.25	16.90
264.9	600.80	112.53	18.73	3.58	16.80
147.2	598.64	223.73	37.37	3.22	10.90
17559.46	10000.00	9320.73	93.21	46.17	48.70
22.13	268.58	57.96	5.13	0.00	6.00
2133.84	1891.89	1117.74	39.85	7.55	20.15
4562.63	2625.63	2306.03	24.53	9.91	10.62

		Pb			
C_{BAC}	%IVBA	ΣF1+F2+F3 BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA
1.58	14.02	97.96	88.36	38.23	43.3
3.40	16.92	106.31	68.55	21.93	32.0
2.30	27.11	144.49	5469.00	1500.22	27.4
4.36	16.53	166.01	305.70	170.69	55.8
4.36	16.25	92.75	490.32	124.00	25.3
14.66	36.03	100.79	190.30	113.05	59.4
3.76	14.68	105.46	650.61	298.88	45.9
24.18	49.65	251.10	594.09	365.55	61.5
3.45	14.55	124.00	176.07	84.87	48.2
1.49	8.24	68.65	297.30	83.60	28.1
3.35	18.92	116.56	228.85	31.48	13.8
3.34	26.73	12.60	611.15	376.58	61.6
1.41	23.42	237.17	683.57	376.26	55.0
5.44	14.42	58.84	1224.72	766.57	62.6
5.77	25.77	76.52	83.64	60.61	72.5
2.53	33.79	95.06	403.05	119.76	29.7
3.45	17.33	98.58	282.33	204.33	72.4
2.61	10.86	136.79	188.21	111.73	59.4
2.35	22.16	118.76	261.29	142.67	54.6
4.80	37.80	129.75	253.81	73.93	29.1
3.01	16.64	134.32	487.45	162.43	33.3
1.34	7.92	71.64	97.02	28.15	29.0
2.15	12.80	208.47	294.59	129.00	43.8
1.30	11.89	150.19	144.27	71.56	49.6
24.18	49.65	251.10	5469.00	1500.22	72.5
1.30	7.92	12.60	68.55	21.93	13.8
4.43	20.60	120.95	565.59	227.34	45.6
4.99	10.31	54.45	1076.94	317.99	16.3

Zn				
%RBA	ΣF1+F2+F3 BCR	Pseudototal	C_{BAC}	%IVBA
37.64	136.9	215.70	75.72	35.11
27.39	31.4	74.60	26.08	34.96
23.25	3481.4	414.00	258.36	62.41
49.07	279.3	521.80	168.41	32.28
21.30	353.9	734.50	241.69	32.91
52.32	791.3	1100.50	933.45	84.82
40.07	647.1	982.70	595.17	60.56
54.25	2907.1	3512.70	2240.61	63.79
42.13	1424.3	1856.70	1204.41	64.87
23.87	184.9	321.10	182.56	56.85
10.81	559.1	707.90	384.33	54.29
54.33	1075.9	1527.90	942.49	61.69
48.35	380.8	1345.80	203.10	15.09
55.21	1988.8	4010.60	1396.01	34.81
64.18	504.8	1049.10	731.59	69.73
25.32	412.5	582.70	478.60	82.14
64.10	889.8	1305.70	1010.83	77.42
52.28	311.6	545.20	136.32	25.00
47.95	409.9	604.60	429.76	71.08
24.79	553.1	2241.80	266.46	11.89
28.60	981.5	4706.70	1614.79	34.31
24.69	41.8	496.70	190.82	38.42
38.12	353.9	828.30	328.49	39.66
43.40	122.8	246.20	66.65	27.07
64.18	3481.39	4706.70	2240.61	84.82
10.81	31.39	74.60	26.08	11.89
39.73	784.32	1247.23	587.78	48.80
14.83	874.81	1224.38	568.78	21.13

Sample	As			
	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			
	CDD			
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion Adjusted value	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact
7	5.45E-06	1.30E-06	6.01E-10	3.66E-09
76*	1.26E-03	4.27E-04	1.39E-07	8.49E-07
77*	1.29E-04	6.72E-05	1.43E-08	8.70E-08
90	3.09E-04	1.78E-04	3.40E-08	2.07E-07
91	9.22E-05	6.78E-05	1.02E-08	6.19E-08
97	4.29E-04	2.51E-04	4.73E-08	2.88E-07
107	2.55E-04	1.31E-04	2.82E-08	1.71E-07
117	1.48E-04	3.40E-05	1.63E-08	9.94E-08
121	1.69E-04	8.33E-05	1.86E-08	1.13E-07
124	1.33E-04	3.25E-05	1.47E-08	8.96E-08
134	1.23E-04	5.49E-05	1.35E-08	8.24E-08
135*	1.80E-04	1.07E-04	1.99E-08	1.21E-07
136*	2.26E-04	1.46E-04	2.50E-08	1.52E-07
145*	7.72E-05	3.07E-05	8.52E-09	5.19E-08
146*	6.70E-05	2.34E-05	7.39E-09	4.50E-08
149	1.23E-04	4.87E-05	1.36E-08	8.25E-08
160	9.94E-05	1.61E-05	1.10E-08	6.68E-08
163	4.24E-05	8.47E-06	4.67E-09	2.85E-08
182	4.14E-05	9.62E-06	4.56E-09	2.78E-08
184	1.38E-05	1.61E-06	1.53E-09	9.29E-09
190	3.97E-05	1.06E-05	4.38E-09	2.66E-08
219	4.54E-05	6.11E-06	5.01E-09	3.05E-08
Mean	1.82E-04	7.89E-05	2.01E-08	1.23E-07
Std. Dev.	2.62E-04	1.01E-04	2.90E-08	1.76E-07
Median	1.23E-04	4.14E-05	1.35E-08	8.25E-08
Max	1.26E-03	4.27E-04	1.39E-07	8.49E-07
Min	5.45E-06	1.30E-06	6.01E-10	3.66E-09

Cancer risk TCR _{As} (unitless)	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)		
	CDD		
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion
1.97E-06	1.27E-05	3.04E-06	1.40E-09
6.43E-04	2.95E-03	9.96E-04	3.25E-07
1.01E-04	3.02E-04	1.57E-04	3.33E-08
2.67E-04	7.20E-04	4.15E-04	7.94E-08
1.02E-04	2.15E-04	1.58E-04	2.37E-08
3.78E-04	1.00E-03	5.86E-04	1.10E-07
1.97E-04	5.96E-04	3.06E-04	6.57E-08
5.14E-05	3.45E-04	7.94E-05	3.81E-08
1.25E-04	3.94E-04	1.94E-04	4.34E-08
4.90E-05	3.11E-04	7.58E-05	3.43E-08
8.27E-05	2.86E-04	1.28E-04	3.16E-08
1.60E-04	4.20E-04	2.49E-04	4.64E-08
2.20E-04	5.28E-04	3.41E-04	5.82E-08
4.63E-05	1.80E-04	7.17E-05	1.99E-08
3.53E-05	1.56E-04	5.46E-05	1.72E-08
7.34E-05	2.87E-04	1.14E-04	3.16E-08
2.43E-05	2.32E-04	3.75E-05	2.56E-08
1.28E-05	9.89E-05	1.98E-05	1.09E-08
1.45E-05	9.66E-05	2.24E-05	1.07E-08
2.44E-06	3.23E-05	3.75E-06	3.56E-09
1.60E-05	9.26E-05	2.47E-05	1.02E-08
9.28E-06	1.06E-04	1.43E-05	1.17E-08
1.19E-04	4.26E-04	1.84E-04	4.69E-08
1.53E-04	6.12E-04	2.36E-04	6.76E-08
6.24E-05	2.86E-04	9.65E-05	3.16E-08
6.43E-04	2.95E-03	9.96E-04	3.25E-07
1.97E-06	1.27E-05	3.04E-06	1.40E-09

		Co	
	Hazard Quotient (HQ _{As}) (unitless)	Total toxicant int	
Skin contact		Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected
8.54E-09	0.01	7.71E-06	2.85E-06
1.98E-06	3.34	1.58E-04	1.81E-05
2.03E-07	0.52	2.66E-05	9.75E-06
4.84E-07	1.39	2.13E-05	9.71E-06
1.45E-07	0.53	5.61E-05	4.18E-05
6.73E-07	1.96	1.89E-05	5.84E-06
4.00E-07	1.02	1.77E-04	1.23E-04
2.32E-07	0.27	3.23E-05	1.41E-05
2.64E-07	0.65	1.14E-05	3.98E-06
2.09E-07	0.25	2.73E-05	9.62E-06
1.92E-07	0.43	2.57E-05	4.22E-06
2.82E-07	0.83	2.59E-05	3.94E-06
3.55E-07	1.14	5.53E-05	1.02E-05
1.21E-07	0.24	1.23E-05	7.98E-06
1.05E-07	0.18	2.49E-05	8.96E-06
1.93E-07	0.38	2.46E-05	1.03E-05
1.56E-07	0.13	1.83E-05	9.36E-06
6.64E-08	0.07	5.39E-05	8.25E-06
6.49E-08	0.08	6.44E-05	1.99E-05
2.17E-08	0.01	1.87E-05	2.43E-06
6.22E-08	0.08	2.26E-05	5.91E-06
7.12E-08	0.05	7.71E-06	3.47E-06
2.86E-07	0.62	4.05E-05	1.52E-05
4.11E-07	0.79	4.41E-05	2.55E-05
1.92E-07	0.32	2.53E-05	9.16E-06
1.98E-06	3.34	1.77E-04	1.23E-04
8.54E-09	0.01	7.71E-06	2.43E-06

			Cu
Intake (mg/kg-day)		Hazard Quotient (HQ _{Co}) (unitless)	Soil ingestion
ADD			
Inhalation	ingestion	Skin contact	
8.51E-10		1.73E-08	2.78E-03
1.74E-08		3.53E-07	3.84E-04
2.93E-09		5.95E-08	1.05E-03
2.35E-09		4.77E-08	1.42E-03
6.19E-09		1.26E-07	1.69E-03
2.08E-09		4.22E-08	1.44E-03
1.95E-08		3.96E-07	2.58E-03
3.56E-09		7.23E-08	8.97E-04
1.26E-09		2.56E-08	1.09E-03
3.01E-09		6.11E-08	6.04E-03
2.84E-09		5.76E-08	1.43E-02
2.85E-09		5.79E-08	1.01E-03
6.10E-09		1.24E-07	1.43E-02
1.36E-09		2.75E-08	1.50E-03
2.74E-09		5.57E-08	2.70E-03
2.71E-09		5.50E-08	1.07E-03
2.02E-09		4.09E-08	1.38E-03
5.94E-09		1.21E-07	1.40E-03
7.11E-09		1.44E-07	1.84E-03
2.06E-09		4.19E-08	8.89E-04
2.49E-09		5.05E-08	8.58E-04
8.51E-10		1.73E-08	8.55E-04
4.46E-09		9.06E-08	2.79E-03
4.86E-09		9.87E-08	3.90E-03
2.79E-09		5.66E-08	1.41E-03
1.95E-08		3.96E-07	1.43E-02
8.51E-10		1.73E-08	3.84E-04

Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			Hazard Quotient (HQ _{Cu}) (unitless)
CDD			
Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact	
1.43E-04	3.06E-07	6.22E-06	0.004
8.28E-05	4.23E-08	2.58E-07	0.002
3.85E-04	1.16E-07	7.04E-07	0.010
4.51E-04	1.57E-07	9.56E-07	0.011
1.48E-03	1.86E-07	1.13E-06	0.037
4.46E-04	1.59E-07	9.70E-07	0.011
2.34E-03	2.85E-07	1.73E-06	0.059
2.32E-04	9.90E-08	6.03E-07	0.006
3.68E-04	1.20E-07	7.33E-07	0.009
3.76E-03	6.66E-07	4.05E-06	0.094
1.04E-02	1.58E-06	9.60E-06	0.261
3.56E-04	1.12E-07	6.81E-07	0.009
1.33E-02	1.58E-06	9.60E-06	0.334
6.78E-04	1.66E-07	1.01E-06	0.017
4.88E-04	2.98E-07	1.81E-06	0.012
3.58E-04	1.18E-07	7.18E-07	0.009
6.55E-04	1.52E-07	9.27E-07	0.016
5.40E-04	1.54E-07	9.40E-07	0.014
2.44E-04	2.03E-07	1.24E-06	0.006
3.18E-04	9.81E-08	5.97E-07	0.008
1.61E-04	9.47E-08	5.77E-07	0.004
3.20E-04	9.43E-08	5.74E-07	0.008
1.71E-03	3.08E-07	2.07E-06	0.043
3.42E-03	4.30E-07	2.78E-06	0.086
4.16E-04	1.56E-07	9.48E-07	0.010
1.33E-02	1.58E-06	9.60E-06	0.334
8.28E-05	4.23E-08	2.58E-07	0.002

Pb			
Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			
CDD			
Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact
5.41E-05	2.04E-05	5.97E-09	1.21E-07
3.35E-03	7.78E-04	3.69E-07	7.50E-06
1.87E-04	9.18E-05	2.06E-08	4.19E-07
3.00E-04	6.39E-05	3.31E-08	6.72E-07
1.17E-04	6.10E-05	1.29E-08	2.61E-07
3.98E-04	1.60E-04	4.39E-08	8.92E-07
3.64E-04	1.97E-04	4.01E-08	8.14E-07
1.08E-04	4.54E-05	1.19E-08	2.41E-07
1.82E-04	4.35E-05	2.01E-08	4.08E-07
1.40E-04	1.52E-05	1.55E-08	3.14E-07
3.74E-04	2.03E-04	4.13E-08	8.38E-07
4.19E-04	2.02E-04	4.62E-08	9.37E-07
7.50E-04	4.14E-04	8.27E-08	1.68E-06
2.47E-04	6.25E-05	2.72E-08	5.53E-07
1.73E-04	1.11E-04	1.91E-08	3.87E-07
1.15E-04	6.02E-05	1.27E-08	2.58E-07
1.60E-04	7.67E-05	1.76E-08	3.58E-07
1.55E-04	3.85E-05	1.71E-08	3.48E-07
2.98E-04	8.54E-05	3.29E-08	6.68E-07
5.94E-05	1.47E-05	6.55E-09	1.33E-07
1.80E-04	6.88E-05	1.99E-08	4.04E-07
8.83E-05	3.83E-05	9.74E-09	1.98E-07
3.74E-04	1.30E-04	4.12E-08	8.36E-07
6.83E-04	1.71E-04	7.54E-08	1.53E-06
1.81E-04	6.63E-05	2.00E-08	4.06E-07
3.35E-03	7.78E-04	3.69E-07	7.50E-06
5.41E-05	1.47E-05	5.97E-09	1.21E-07

Cancer risk TCR _{Pb} (unitless)	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)		
	CDD		
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion
3.00E-07	1.26E-04	4.75E-05	1.39E-08
1.45E-05	7.81E-03	1.82E-03	8.62E-07
1.22E-06	4.37E-04	2.14E-04	4.82E-08
1.25E-06	7.00E-04	1.49E-04	7.73E-08
7.92E-07	2.72E-04	1.42E-04	3.00E-08
2.29E-06	9.29E-04	3.72E-04	1.03E-07
2.53E-06	8.49E-04	4.60E-04	9.36E-08
6.39E-07	2.52E-04	1.06E-04	2.77E-08
7.97E-07	4.25E-04	1.01E-04	4.68E-08
4.58E-07	3.27E-04	3.54E-05	3.61E-08
2.61E-06	8.73E-04	4.74E-04	9.63E-08
2.70E-06	9.77E-04	4.72E-04	1.08E-07
5.28E-06	1.75E-03	9.66E-04	1.93E-07
1.11E-06	5.76E-04	1.46E-04	6.35E-08
1.35E-06	4.03E-04	2.59E-04	4.45E-08
7.83E-07	2.69E-04	1.41E-04	2.97E-08
1.03E-06	3.73E-04	1.79E-04	4.12E-08
6.92E-07	3.63E-04	8.99E-05	4.00E-08
1.43E-06	6.96E-04	1.99E-04	7.68E-08
2.64E-07	1.39E-04	3.42E-05	1.53E-08
1.01E-06	4.21E-04	1.60E-04	4.64E-08
5.33E-07	2.06E-04	8.94E-05	2.27E-08
1.98E-06	8.72E-04	3.02E-04	9.61E-08
3.01E-06	1.59E-03	4.00E-04	1.76E-07
1.07E-06	4.23E-04	1.55E-04	4.66E-08
1.45E-05	7.81E-03	1.82E-03	8.62E-07
2.64E-07	1.26E-04	3.42E-05	1.39E-08

	Hazard Quotient (HQ_{Pb}) (unitless)	Hazard Index HI (unitless)
Skin contact		
2.83E-07	0.09	0.11
1.75E-05	5.61	8.96
9.78E-07	0.31	0.85
1.57E-06	0.50	1.90
6.09E-07	0.20	0.76
2.08E-06	0.67	2.64
1.90E-06	0.61	1.70
5.63E-07	0.18	0.45
9.51E-07	0.31	0.97
7.32E-07	0.23	0.58
1.95E-06	0.63	1.32
2.19E-06	0.70	1.54
3.92E-06	1.26	2.73
1.29E-06	0.41	0.67
9.03E-07	0.29	0.49
6.02E-07	0.19	0.58
8.36E-07	0.27	0.41
8.12E-07	0.26	0.34
1.56E-06	0.50	0.58
3.10E-07	0.10	0.12
9.42E-07	0.30	0.39
4.61E-07	0.15	0.20
1.95E-06	0.63	1.29
3.57E-06	1.15	1.87
9.47E-07	0.30	0.63
1.75E-05	5.61	8.96
2.83E-07	0.09	0.11

Sample	As			
	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			
	CDD			
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion Adjusted value	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact
7	7.63E-06	1.82E-06	8.97E-12	1.40E-10
76*	1.77E-03	5.98E-04	2.08E-09	3.25E-08
77*	1.81E-04	9.41E-05	2.13E-10	3.33E-09
90	4.32E-04	2.49E-04	5.08E-10	7.94E-09
91	1.29E-04	9.49E-05	1.52E-10	2.37E-09
97	6.01E-04	3.52E-04	7.07E-10	1.10E-08
107	3.57E-04	1.84E-04	4.20E-10	6.57E-09
117	2.07E-04	4.76E-05	2.44E-10	3.81E-09
121	2.36E-04	1.17E-04	2.78E-10	4.34E-09
124	1.87E-04	4.55E-05	2.20E-10	3.43E-09
134	1.72E-04	7.69E-05	2.02E-10	3.16E-09
135*	2.52E-04	1.49E-04	2.97E-10	4.64E-09
136*	3.17E-04	2.05E-04	3.73E-10	5.82E-09
145*	1.08E-04	4.30E-05	1.27E-10	1.99E-09
146*	9.38E-05	3.28E-05	1.10E-10	1.72E-09
149	1.72E-04	6.82E-05	2.02E-10	3.16E-09
160	1.39E-04	2.25E-05	1.64E-10	2.56E-09
163	5.93E-05	1.19E-05	6.98E-11	1.09E-09
182	5.79E-05	1.35E-05	6.82E-11	1.07E-09
184	1.94E-05	2.25E-06	2.28E-11	3.56E-10
190	5.55E-05	1.48E-05	6.53E-11	1.02E-09
219	6.36E-05	8.56E-06	7.48E-11	1.17E-09
Mean	2.55E-04	1.10E-04	3.00E-10	4.69E-09
Std. Dev.	3.67E-04	1.42E-04	4.32E-10	6.76E-09
Median	1.72E-04	5.79E-05	2.02E-10	3.16E-09
Max	1.77E-03	5.98E-04	2.08E-09	3.25E-08
Min	7.63E-06	1.82E-06	8.97E-12	1.40E-10

Cancer risk TCR _{As} (unitless)	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)		
	CDD		
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion
2.74E-06	8.90E-05	2.13E-05	1.64E-09
8.97E-04	2.07E-02	6.97E-03	3.80E-07
1.41E-04	2.12E-03	1.10E-03	3.89E-08
3.73E-04	5.04E-03	2.90E-03	9.27E-08
1.42E-04	1.51E-03	1.11E-03	2.77E-08
5.28E-04	7.01E-03	4.10E-03	1.29E-07
2.76E-04	4.17E-03	2.14E-03	7.66E-08
7.14E-05	2.42E-03	5.56E-04	4.44E-08
1.75E-04	2.76E-03	1.36E-03	5.07E-08
6.82E-05	2.18E-03	5.30E-04	4.00E-08
1.15E-04	2.00E-03	8.97E-04	3.68E-08
2.24E-04	2.94E-03	1.74E-03	5.41E-08
3.07E-04	3.70E-03	2.39E-03	6.79E-08
6.45E-05	1.26E-03	5.02E-04	2.32E-08
4.92E-05	1.09E-03	3.82E-04	2.01E-08
1.02E-04	2.01E-03	7.96E-04	3.69E-08
3.37E-05	1.62E-03	2.62E-04	2.99E-08
1.78E-05	6.92E-04	1.38E-04	1.27E-08
2.02E-05	6.76E-04	1.57E-04	1.24E-08
3.37E-06	2.26E-04	2.62E-05	4.15E-09
2.23E-05	6.48E-04	1.73E-04	1.19E-08
1.28E-05	7.42E-04	9.98E-05	1.36E-08
1.66E-04	2.98E-03	1.29E-03	5.48E-08
2.13E-04	4.29E-03	1.66E-03	7.88E-08
8.69E-05	2.01E-03	6.76E-04	3.69E-08
8.97E-04	2.07E-02	6.97E-03	3.80E-07
2.74E-06	8.90E-05	2.13E-05	1.64E-09

		Co	
	Hazard Quotient (HQ _{As}) (unitless)	Total toxicant int	
Skin contact		Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected
1.05E-10	0.07	5.40E-05	1.99E-05
2.43E-08	23.25	1.10E-03	1.27E-04
2.49E-09	3.66	1.86E-04	6.82E-05
5.93E-09	9.68	1.49E-04	6.80E-05
1.77E-09	3.69	3.93E-04	2.93E-04
8.25E-09	13.68	1.32E-04	4.09E-05
4.90E-09	7.14	1.24E-03	8.61E-04
2.84E-09	1.85	2.26E-04	9.88E-05
3.24E-09	4.54	8.00E-05	2.79E-05
2.56E-09	1.77	1.91E-04	6.73E-05
2.36E-09	2.99	1.80E-04	2.95E-05
3.46E-09	5.80	1.81E-04	2.76E-05
4.35E-09	7.97	3.87E-04	7.15E-05
1.48E-09	1.67	8.60E-05	5.58E-05
1.29E-09	1.28	1.74E-04	6.27E-05
2.36E-09	2.65	1.72E-04	7.23E-05
1.91E-09	0.87	1.28E-04	6.55E-05
8.14E-10	0.46	3.77E-04	5.78E-05
7.95E-10	0.52	4.51E-04	1.39E-04
2.66E-10	0.09	1.31E-04	1.70E-05
7.62E-10	0.58	1.58E-04	4.14E-05
8.73E-10	0.33	5.40E-05	2.43E-05
3.51E-09	4.30	2.83E-04	1.06E-04
5.04E-09	5.52	3.09E-04	1.79E-04
2.36E-09	2.25	1.77E-04	6.41E-05
2.43E-08	23.2	1.24E-03	8.61E-04
1.05E-10	0.07	5.40E-05	1.70E-05

			Cu
Intake (mg/kg-day)		Hazard Quotient (HQ _{Co}) (unitless)	Soil ingestion
Inhalation	Skin contact		
9.93E-10	6.35E-11	0.0007	1.95E-02
2.03E-08	1.30E-09	0.0042	2.69E-03
3.42E-09	2.19E-10	0.0023	7.34E-03
2.74E-09	1.75E-10	0.0023	9.96E-03
7.22E-09	4.62E-10	0.0098	1.18E-02
2.43E-09	1.55E-10	0.0014	1.01E-02
2.27E-08	1.46E-09	0.0287	1.81E-02
4.15E-09	2.66E-10	0.0033	6.28E-03
1.47E-09	9.41E-11	0.0009	7.64E-03
3.51E-09	2.25E-10	0.0022	4.23E-02
3.31E-09	2.12E-10	0.0010	1.00E-01
3.33E-09	2.13E-10	0.0009	7.10E-03
7.11E-09	4.55E-10	0.0024	1.00E-01
1.58E-09	1.01E-10	0.0019	1.05E-02
3.20E-09	2.05E-10	0.0021	1.89E-02
3.16E-09	2.02E-10	0.0024	7.48E-03
2.35E-09	1.51E-10	0.0022	9.67E-03
6.93E-09	4.44E-10	0.0019	9.80E-03
8.29E-09	5.31E-10	0.0046	1.29E-02
2.41E-09	1.54E-10	0.0006	6.23E-03
2.90E-09	1.86E-10	0.0014	6.01E-03
9.93E-10	6.35E-11	0.0008	5.99E-03
5.21E-09	3.33E-10	0.0035	1.96E-02
5.67E-09	3.63E-10	0.0060	2.73E-02
3.25E-09	2.08E-10	0.0021	9.88E-03
2.27E-08	1.46E-09	0.0287	1.00E-01
9.93E-10	6.35E-11	0.0006	2.69E-03

Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			Hazard Quotient (HQ _{Cu}) (unitless)
CDD			
Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact	
9.98E-04	3.58E-07	2.29E-08	0.02
5.80E-04	4.94E-08	3.16E-09	0.01
2.70E-03	1.35E-07	8.63E-09	0.07
3.16E-03	1.83E-07	1.17E-08	0.08
1.04E-02	2.17E-07	1.39E-08	0.26
3.12E-03	1.86E-07	1.19E-08	0.08
1.64E-02	3.32E-07	2.13E-08	0.41
1.63E-03	1.15E-07	7.39E-09	0.04
2.58E-03	1.40E-07	8.99E-09	0.06
2.63E-02	7.77E-07	4.97E-08	0.66
7.29E-02	1.84E-06	1.18E-07	1.82
2.49E-03	1.30E-07	8.35E-09	0.06
9.32E-02	1.84E-06	1.18E-07	2.33
4.75E-03	1.94E-07	1.24E-08	0.12
3.41E-03	3.47E-07	2.22E-08	0.09
2.51E-03	1.38E-07	8.80E-09	0.06
4.58E-03	1.78E-07	1.14E-08	0.11
3.78E-03	1.80E-07	1.15E-08	0.09
1.71E-03	2.37E-07	1.51E-08	0.04
2.23E-03	1.14E-07	7.32E-09	0.06
1.13E-03	1.10E-07	7.07E-09	0.03
2.24E-03	1.10E-07	7.04E-09	0.06
1.19E-02	3.59E-07	2.30E-08	0.30
2.40E-02	5.01E-07	3.21E-08	0.60
2.91E-03	1.82E-07	1.16E-08	0.07
9.32E-02	1.84E-06	1.18E-07	2.33
5.80E-04	4.94E-08	3.16E-09	0.01

Pb			
Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)			
CDD			
Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion	Skin contact
7.57E-05	2.85E-05	1.39E-09	8.91E-11
4.69E-03	1.09E-03	8.62E-08	5.51E-09
2.62E-04	1.29E-04	4.82E-09	3.08E-10
4.20E-04	8.95E-05	7.73E-09	4.94E-10
1.63E-04	8.53E-05	3.00E-09	1.92E-10
5.58E-04	2.23E-04	1.03E-08	6.56E-10
5.09E-04	2.76E-04	9.36E-09	5.99E-10
1.51E-04	6.36E-05	2.77E-09	1.78E-10
2.55E-04	6.08E-05	4.68E-09	3.00E-10
1.96E-04	2.12E-05	3.61E-09	2.31E-10
5.24E-04	2.85E-04	9.63E-09	6.16E-10
5.86E-04	2.83E-04	1.08E-08	6.89E-10
1.05E-03	5.80E-04	1.93E-08	1.24E-09
3.45E-04	8.75E-05	6.35E-09	4.06E-10
2.42E-04	1.55E-04	4.45E-09	2.85E-10
1.61E-04	8.43E-05	2.97E-09	1.90E-10
2.24E-04	1.07E-04	4.12E-09	2.63E-10
2.18E-04	5.39E-05	4.00E-09	2.56E-10
4.18E-04	1.20E-04	7.68E-09	4.92E-10
8.32E-05	2.05E-05	1.53E-09	9.78E-11
2.53E-04	9.63E-05	4.64E-09	2.97E-10
1.24E-04	5.37E-05	2.27E-09	1.45E-10
5.23E-04	1.81E-04	9.61E-09	6.15E-10
9.57E-04	2.40E-04	1.76E-08	1.13E-09
2.54E-04	9.29E-05	4.66E-09	2.98E-10
4.69E-03	1.09E-03	8.62E-08	5.51E-09
7.57E-05	2.05E-05	1.39E-09	8.91E-11

Cancer risk TCR _{Pb} (unitless)	Total toxicant intake (mg/kg-day)		
	CDD		
	Soil ingestion	Soil ingestion corrected	Inhalation ingestion
2.44E-07	8.84E-04	3.33E-04	1.62E-08
9.35E-06	5.47E-02	1.27E-02	1.01E-06
1.10E-06	3.06E-03	1.50E-03	5.62E-08
7.69E-07	4.90E-03	1.04E-03	9.01E-08
7.29E-07	1.90E-03	9.96E-04	3.50E-08
1.91E-06	6.51E-03	2.61E-03	1.20E-07
2.36E-06	5.94E-03	3.22E-03	1.09E-07
5.43E-07	1.76E-03	7.42E-04	3.24E-08
5.22E-07	2.97E-03	7.10E-04	5.47E-08
1.84E-07	2.29E-03	2.47E-04	4.21E-08
2.43E-06	6.11E-03	3.32E-03	1.12E-07
2.42E-06	6.84E-03	3.30E-03	1.26E-07
4.95E-06	1.22E-02	6.76E-03	2.25E-07
7.50E-07	4.03E-03	1.02E-03	7.41E-08
1.32E-06	2.82E-03	1.81E-03	5.19E-08
7.20E-07	1.88E-03	9.84E-04	3.46E-08
9.17E-07	2.61E-03	1.25E-03	4.80E-08
4.63E-07	2.54E-03	6.29E-04	4.67E-08
1.02E-06	4.87E-03	1.39E-03	8.96E-08
1.76E-07	9.70E-04	2.40E-04	1.78E-08
8.23E-07	2.95E-03	1.12E-03	5.42E-08
4.59E-07	1.44E-03	6.26E-04	2.65E-08
1.55E-06	6.10E-03	2.12E-03	1.12E-07
2.06E-06	1.12E-02	2.80E-03	2.05E-07
7.96E-07	2.96E-03	1.08E-03	5.44E-08
9.35E-06	5.47E-02	1.27E-02	1.01E-06
1.76E-07	8.84E-04	2.40E-04	1.62E-08

	Hazard Quotient	Hazard Index
	(HQ_{Pb})	HI
Skin contact	(unitless)	(unitless)
1.04E-09	0.24	0.3
6.43E-08	9.08	32.3
3.60E-09	1.07	4.80
5.77E-09	0.75	10.5
2.24E-09	0.71	4.67
7.65E-09	1.86	15.6
6.99E-09	2.30	9.88
2.07E-09	0.53	2.43
3.50E-09	0.51	5.11
2.69E-09	0.18	2.60
7.19E-09	2.37	7.19
8.04E-09	2.36	8.23
1.44E-08	4.83	15.1
4.74E-09	0.73	2.52
3.32E-09	1.29	2.66
2.21E-09	0.70	3.42
3.07E-09	0.89	1.89
2.99E-09	0.45	1.01
5.73E-09	1.00	1.57
1.14E-09	0.17	0.31
3.47E-09	0.80	1.41
1.70E-09	0.45	0.84
7.18E-09	1.51	6.11
1.31E-08	2.00	7.38
3.48E-09	0.77	3.04
6.43E-08	9.08	32.3
1.04E-09	0.17	0.31